

D1.1: Market Analysis and Innovation Drivers

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Status: Final

Submission date: November 30, 2023

Summary Sheet

Deliverable number	D1.1
Deliverable title	Market Analysis and Innovation Drivers
Document ID	GEMINI_D1.1_ Market Analysis and Innovation Drivers
Project number	101103801
Project name	Greening European Mobility through cascading innovation INItiatives
Work Package	WP1
Contractual submission date	30 November 2023
Actual submission date	29 November 2023
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Lead beneficiary	UPM
Responsible authors	Laura Garrido, Thais Rangel, Diana Patricia Naranjo, José Manuel Vassallo
Contributing authors (Beneficiary)	John Limaxis (INLE)
About this deliverable	Report consolidating market situation and factors to be considered in the design of NMS business models to be tested in the MLLs, mapped to technical and social innovation drivers (Task 1.1).
Keywords	New and Shared Mobility Services; Business Models; Key Societal Goals; Innovation drivers.
Acknowledgments	To all GEMINI partners that have collaborated indirectly in this deliverable through the templates used to collect information on shared mobility business models and to develop the survey (See Section 2).
Disclaimer	Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Version	Date	% Complete	Details/ Changes	Reviewers Name (Beneficiary), Date of review
V1	07/11/23	95%	First draft	Katariina Köykkä (SIN), 16/11/23 Amalia Polydoropoulou (UAEGEAN), 18/11/23
V2	27/11/23	100%	Final draft	Vera-Marie Andrieu (UEMI), 29/11/23
V3	29/11/23	100%	Final	
V4	09/06/25		Revision based on CINEA comments	Oliver Lah (UEMI) 09/06/25

GEMINI (Grant Agreement No. 101103801) is an Innovation Action project funded by the EU Framework Programme Horizon Europe. This document contains information about GEMINI core activities, findings, and outcomes.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronyms	Full meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
BM	Business model
CDS-M	Common Data Sharing Methodology
DRT	Demand Responsive Transit
FFCS	Free-Floating Car Sharing
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gas Emissions
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communication
ICT	Information Communications Technology
IDS	Intrusion Detection Systems
IoT	Internet of Things
MaaS	Mobility as a Commons
MaaS	Mobility-as-a-Service
MLL	Mobility Living Lab
MSP	Mobility Service Provider
NMS	New and Shared Mobility Services
NOx	Nitrogen Oxides
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PKI	Public-Private Key Infrastructures
PM	Particulate Matter
PT	Public Transport
SaaS	Software as a Service

SUMP	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan
TPM	Trusted Platform Modules
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Shared mobility has the potential to become an important driver of sustainable mobility. GEMINI's vision is to accelerate the progress towards climate neutrality by reinforcing modal shift through the demonstration and uptake of new shared mobility services (NMS), active transport modes, and micromobility and their integration with public transport (PT) in new generation MaaS services. Drivers of this transition will be the GEMINI Mobility Living Labs (MLL) in 8 mission cities, engaging local communities in the implementation of their SUMP (Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans) and the co-creation, development and adoption of promising innovative mobility solutions. The MLLs will stimulate improved access to PT whilst introducing sustainable mobility business models in urban and peri-urban contexts, in turn leading to changes in mobility patterns and behaviours, aimed at less car-centred urban mobility systems.

The present deliverable D1.1 *Market Analysis and Innovation Drivers* aims to identify key inputs that need to be considered for the right design of NMS business models from a threefold perspective.

First, the deliverable identifies the successes and failures of NMS business models already implemented. This will facilitate the definition and success of the value propositions to be tested in the MLLs. To provide this knowledge, this deliverable provides a literature review on benefits, challenges, successes, and failures of NMS business models reported by previous studies (see [Section 3](#)), which has been complemented by practical insight from the experience of GEMINI partners actively involved in the implementation of NMS business models (see Appendixes [B](#) to [JJ](#)). A summary of the main benefits, issues and challenges of shared mobility is displayed in [Section 3.3](#).

Second, the deliverable identifies and prioritises key societal goals that NMS are supposed to improve (see [Section 4.2](#)). This will contribute to setting specific outputs for the impact assessment of the business models. The key goals that were considered most important for society and that NMS can contribute most belong to the social and environmental categories. Particularly, "*Improve air quality in cities*", "*Mitigate climate change*", "*Reduce energy consumption*" and "*Reduce natural resources consumption*" in the environmental category and "*Better use of public space*", "*Accessibility and proximity to goods and services*", and "*Accessibility for people with reduced mobility*" in the social category were the highest rated in both aspects.

Third, the deliverable maps emerging innovation drivers from the social (see [Section 4.3](#)) and technical (see [Section 4.4](#)) perspective that may affect mobility business models, and hence should be considered at the time of designing NMS.

On the social side, the current major social trends expected to positively influence the adoption and frequency of use of NMS the most were "*Detachment of car ownership*", "*Sustainability and environmental concerns*", "*User's demand for a greater quality of service*" and "*Working from home culture*". In contrast, "*Aging of the population*" should be seen as a threat to the successful implementation of NMS. Thus, NMS business models should consider the needs of the elderly to gain potential in the future.

On the technical side, "*Physical and ICT (Information Communications Technology) infrastructure*" was seen as the technology enabler with the highest potential to change the current mobility landscape. The technologies considered to have the greatest potential to drive NMS innovation were "*Advanced fleet monitoring and management solutions*", "*IoT (Internet of Things) infrastructure and smart cities*", "*Big Data, AI and machine learning techniques*" and "*Connected, cooperative and autonomous vehicles*". The service-related NMS attributes to which new

technologies are expected to contribute most to improve were "*Modal integration*", "*User experience, customer satisfaction, and quality of service*", and "*Accessibility and proximity of transport services to people*". In that framework, MaaS appeared to be the specific NMS that is expected to take greater advantage of new technologies. Finally, the main challenges to promoting the integration of technical innovations into NMS were "*Regulatory hurdles*" and "*Availability of infrastructure (physical and ICT)*".

The results on key societal goals and social and technical innovation drivers were founded on an online survey addressed to mobility experts and key stakeholders, which can be seen in [Appendix JJ](#). A descriptive analysis of the survey is presented in [Section 4.1](#). A summary of the survey results has been also published on the project [website](#).

1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

Shared mobility has emerged as a revolutionary paradigm in the transportation industry, redefining how people access and utilise mobility services in urban and suburban environments. The mobility market is experiencing a revolution driven by the uptake of breakthrough technical and social innovations such as connectivity and automation, digitalisation, clean energies, MaaS, and sophisticated governance and regulation approaches. The right adoption of these innovations is crucial to respond to key societal challenges aimed at improving quality of life such as climate change mitigation, inclusiveness, resilience, safety, efficiency in the use of human and natural resources, etc. Although some new mobility business models have already been deployed, they still face some problems arising from the lack of understanding by users, the issues to coordinate different stakeholders, and the lack of alignment between social and private goals.

The aim of the present deliverable D1.1 *Market Analysis and Innovation Drivers* is to map key inputs necessary for the right design of business models for shared mobility services from a threefold perspective.

- First, the deliverable identifies the fundamental benefits, challenges, successes, and failures of shared mobility business models already reported by previous studies and practical experiences.
- Second, the deliverable identifies and prioritises key societal goals –such as climate change mitigation, inclusiveness, financial sustainability, etc.– that New and Shared Mobility Services (NMS) are supposed to improve.
- And third, the deliverable maps emerging innovation drivers from the social and technical perspective that may affect mobility business models, and hence should be considered at the time of designing NMS.

The results of this analysis will contribute to (i) identifying key challenges to tackle at the time of defining GEMINI business models in T1.2 *New Business Models/Schemes*, and (ii) setting specific outputs for the impact assessment of the business models implemented in the Mobility Living Labs (MLL).

The deliverable is structured as follows. [Section 1](#) serves as the introduction, setting the context and objectives of the research. Then, [Section 2](#) outlines the methodology designed to accomplish the objectives of the deliverable. [Section 3](#) identifies the fundamental benefits, challenges, successes, and failures of shared mobility business models already reported by previous studies and practical experiences and [Section 4](#) the key drivers for the design of GEMINI business models. Finally, [Section 5](#) summarises the main conclusions regarding the benefits and challenges of NMS, their impact on key societal goals, and the emerging social and technical innovation drivers that may affect NMS.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodology designed to accomplish the objectives of the deliverable. The methodology is divided into two sections: (i) the approach outlined to identify benefits, challenges, successes, and failures of business models; and (ii) the survey designed to detect technical and social innovation drivers and key societal goals.

2.1 Identification of benefits, challenges, successes, and failures of business models

The fulfilment of the first objective, that is, the identification of the fundamental benefits, challenges, successes, and failures of shared mobility business models already implemented, has been achieved by undertaking two main actions:

- A comprehensive **literature review** on the topic was conducted by exploring existing knowledge (around 100 research articles and practical reports) in influential scientific databases such as WoS and Scopus. This allowed to identify the benefits, challenges, successes, and failures of the shared mobility services' business models already reported by previous studies.
- **Practical insight from the experience of GEMINI partners** actively involved in the implementation of shared mobility business models was gathered. To that end, a template was designed and made available to all partners through the project Sharepoint to facilitate the collection of information. The specific information collected through the template was (i) the name of the partner providing information, (ii) the shared mobility business model to be reported and a brief description, (iii) case studies where the business model has been applied, (iv) successes, obstacles and/or failures of the business model, and (v) references to academic or grey literature where the case study is discussed. This template can be seen in [Appendix A](#).

The possibility was also offered to share this information through interviews with the authors of this deliverable instead of filling the template.

Overall, 38 templates were received from 13 partners with information on different NMS, three of which were discarded due to incompleteness. In addition, two meetings were held with project partners (TM, VW). The templates with detailed information on shared mobility business models from the partners are available in Appendixes [B](#) to [JJ](#) of this document.

TABLE 1 shows the mobility service business models that were reported in the templates by GEMINI partners, the acronyms used in the deliverable when referring to these templates, the partners providing the templates, the country/countries of operation of the NMS/case studies reported and the Appendix of the deliverable where they are located.

TABLE 1 Summary of the mobility service business models discussed in the templates provided by GEMINI partners

Acronym	Mobility service business model	Partner	Country	App.
Carsharing 1	One-way free floating car sharing in open communities	GoodMoovs	FR	B
Carsharing 2	Two-way station-based car sharing in closed communities	GoodMoovs	NL	C
Carsharing 3	B2C car sharing for neighbourhoods or housing companies	FVH	FI	D
Carsharing 4	Peer-to-peer car sharing	FVH	FI	E
Carsharing 5	Business-to-Consumer (B2C) car sharing	EPF	BE, DE	E
Carsharing 6	Peer-to-Peer (P2P) car sharing	EPF	US, BE, Europe, WW	G
Carsharing 7	Peer-to-Peer (P2P) car sharing	TTS	US, Europe, DK	H

Acronym	Mobility service business model	Partner	Country	App.
Carsharing 8	Car sharing, Modern car club, and Ride-hailing	PD	US, Europe	I
Carsharing 9	B2C car sharing	REGH	DK	J
Carsharing 10	Platform-driven models (B2B, B2C) - Free-floating vehicles	Arriva Dan	DK	K
Carsharing 11	Platform-driven models (B2B, B2C) - Free-floating car sharing	Arriva Dan	Europe	L
Carsharing 12	Platform-driven models (B2B, B2C) - Free-floating car sharing	Arriva Dan	AT	M
Crowdshipping	Crowdshipping	PD	US, UK, FR, SG	N
DRT 1	Demand Responsive Transit (DRT) model.	TTS	FI	O
DRT 2	Demand Responsive Transport (DRT) system	PD	EL	P
MaaS	Mobility as a Common	TM	NL	Q
MaaS 1	Bundle of mobility services with monthly subscription	5T	IT, FI, SE	R
MaaS 2	MSP-Driven MaaS Integration (Mobility Super App)	5T	Europe, WW, IT-US	S
MaaS 3	Integrated mobility platform (Pay-as-you-go)	5T	IT, Europe	T
MaaS 4	B2C MaaS subscription model	FVH	Europe & JP	U
MaaS 5	B2C on-demand door-to-door MaaS travel chain	FVH	FI	V
MaaS 6	MaaS platform based	EPF	Europe, JP, BE	W
MaaS 7	MaaS platform	TTS	SE, FI, IT, SCT	X
MaaS 8	Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS)	ITA	Europe & JP	Y
Micromobility 1	B2C shared cargo bikes for shopping	FVH	FI	Z
Micromobility 2	Business-to-consumer (B2C) shared micromobility	EPF	Europe & IL, BE, NL, DE, SE, WW	AA
Micromobility 3	Bike Share system in Copenhagen and Frederiksberg	REGH	DK	BB
Mobility Hub	Mobility Hub	PD	DE	CC
Other 1	B2C leisure boat sharing	FVH	FI, SE, NO, DK, CA, NZ	DD
Other 2	B2C on-demand electric boat with a half-fixed route	FVH	FI	EE
Ridesharing 1	Sports club ride to training	FVH	FI	FF
Ridesharing 2	Peer-to-Peer (P2P) ridesharing	EPF	WW, BE	GG
Ridesharing 3	Carpooling platform	VVP	PT	HH
Ridesharing 4	Carpooling platform	VVP	PT	II
SaaS	Software as a service (SaaS)	ATOM	SE, LV, UA	JJ

The combined analysis of the literature and the practical insight from organisations actively involved in the implementation of shared mobility business models provides a unique perspective on the real-world successes and challenges faced by key stakeholders in this field.

2.2 Identification of technical and social innovation drivers and key societal goals

The second and third objectives were addressed through an **online survey** targeted towards a variety of stakeholders in the field of mobility. The objective of the survey was to obtain insight for the development of new business models for NMS. The questions of the survey were designed to identify emerging technical and social innovations that could affect these services and to define key societal goals that these services should address.

The survey was designed in the following way. First, UPM shared with the GEMINI partners the following information: (i) a list of experts and key stakeholders of NMS; (ii) a pre-map of emerging technical and social innovation drivers applicable to the business models; and (iii) a draft list of key societal goals that NMS are supposed to improve. Second, GEMINI partners provided feedback on the previous information with the aim of identifying missing aspects to better structure the survey. Third, UPM along with the partners involved in T1.1 *Market Analysis and Innovation Drivers* studied the recommendations and delivered a first version of the survey that was subsequently submitted to all GEMINI partners for additional comments. Finally, taking into consideration those comments, UPM, INLE, TTS and CENEX designed the final version of the survey intending to balance the possibility of obtaining information and the need to reach a high rate of response.

The survey was designed to be answered in approximately 15 minutes. Respondents were asked to answer the questions based on their independent personal opinion, regardless of whether it coincides or not with the point of view of the company/government they work for. The final version of the survey is included in [Appendix KK](#) of the deliverable.

The survey consisted of four parts: (i) respondent characterisation and professional background, (ii) key societal goals, (iii) social innovation drivers, and (iv) technical innovation drivers.

(i) Respondents' profile characterisation and professional background

This section is split into two different parts in the survey: the respondents' characterisation at the beginning of the survey and the professional background at the end of it. The respondents' characterisation determines their level of expertise and usage of NMS. The professional background identifies their working experience (position and years of experience), and attributes of the company they work for such as size, the country where it is based, scope (local, regional...) and whether it is part of the GEMINI consortium or not.

(ii) Key societal goals

This section identifies and prioritises key societal goals –such as climate change mitigation, inclusiveness, financial sustainability, etc.– that NMS are likely to improve. It comprises three questions to evaluate the importance of key goals for society (in absolute and relative terms) and the extent to which NMS will be able to contribute to their achievement.

(iii) Social innovation drivers

This section maps emerging innovation drivers from the social perspective –such as working from home culture, sustainability and environmental concerns, user demand for a greater quality of service, etc.– that may affect mobility business models and hence should be considered at the time of designing NMS. It comprises two questions to evaluate the importance of social trends and the extent to which they can influence (positively or negatively) the adoption and frequency of use of NMS.

(iv) Technical innovation drivers

This section maps emerging innovation drivers from the technical perspective –such as ICT and physical infrastructure, intelligent systems and decision-making solutions, vehicle connectivity innovations, etc.– that may affect mobility business models and hence should be considered at the time of designing NMS. It comprises four questions to evaluate the potential of technical innovation drivers and their impact on NMS, as well as to identify the greatest barriers and challenges they face and the NMS that could benefit the most from their deployment.

The insights obtained through the survey will guide the design of NMS in GEMINI so that they are aligned with both societal needs and business objectives.

3 CHALLENGES OF SHARED MOBILITY BUSINESS MODELS

This section explores the different types of NMS business models, discussing their features, benefits and issues. It starts by examining the fundamental characteristics of shared mobility and its classification, followed by an analysis of various aspects impacting these services.

3.1 Characteristics of Shared Mobility Business Models

To correctly identify and describe NMS is essential to outline the concept of business models applied to them. The concept of business model, introduced and popularised by Osterwalder et al. (2005), has gained widespread recognition and adoption in the business community over the last few years. It provides a framework that describes how a company creates, delivers, and captures value. This concept is often visualised and analysed using tools like the Business Model Canvas, which was developed by Osterwalder & Pigneur (2010).

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) is a visual framework that helps businesses identify key elements of their business model and how they relate to each other. The Canvas is divided into nine key elements: customer segments, value propositions, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure.

Shared mobility, as a new transportation concept, aims to optimise vehicle and space utilisation by providing users with access to vehicles without requiring ownership. NMS are considered to promote sustainability insofar as they replace private modes of transportation (Karbaumer & Metz, 2021). It is important to note that the concept of shared mobility does not include conventional public transport modes such as buses and metro systems. According to the literature (see e.g. Boer et al., 2022; Roukouni & Correia, 2020; Shaheen et al., 2019), shared mobility modes can be classified into the following groups:

- **Shared Micromobility** is used to describe the shared use of low-speed modes such as bicycles, scooters, and mopeds (Shaheen & Cohen, 2019). This group includes a variety of service models and transport modes to meet the needs of travellers such as station-

based bike sharing, where bikes can be conveniently taken and returned to designated stations, as well as dockless bike sharing, where bikes can be taken and returned to any location. These service models are similarly available for scooters and mopeds. Micromobility services are mainly adopted by younger generations.

- **On-demand ride services** include app-based mobility services such as ride-sharing (carpooling and vanpooling), ride-hailing (Uber, Lyft, Didi, etc), e-hailing (app-based operators) and shared-ride automated mobility-on-demand services (SRAMODS)(Hyland & Mahmassani, 2020).
- **Car sharing** provides on-demand access to cars. Individuals can enjoy the advantages of using a private vehicle without incurring the expenses and responsibilities of ownership.
- **Courier network services or crowd-shipping** refer to for-hire delivery services in exchange for monetary compensation using an app to connect couriers using their own vehicles, bicycles, or scooters that agree to deliver packages to the consigners.
- **Demand-responsive transit (DRT)** includes services that operate simultaneously and are often complementary to public transport such as shuttle and micro-transit services.

Shared mobility business models can be examined using the BMC to understand how they create value, deliver services, and remain profitable over time by shaping their operations, prices, partnerships, and customer relationships. In a study conducted by Gilibert & Ribas (2019), the business models of ride-hailing, ridesharing, and car sharing were analysed using the nine building blocks of the BMC. According to the authors, applying BMC has facilitated the identification of common characteristics and differences among these NMS. They found that many building blocks presented more similarities than differences among the services. For instance, the Channels (mainly reach customers through their own service apps or multimodal apps provided by MaaS platforms), Customer Relationships (the three services offer customer support services) and Key Partnerships (involving local governments, public transit, technological platform providers, payment operators, etc.) blocks were common to all three service types.

After comparing the different business models, Gilibert & Ribas (2019) conclude that these services are complementary rather than substitutable, as each one addresses different needs. They also proposed options to enhance the profitability of shared mobility service providers. One option involves an integrated service, which enables users to access various NMS through a single app, thereby increasing customer loyalty and reducing customer acquisition costs. Another option is outsourcing certain key activities (e.g., customer service, development, management and optimisation of the platform, vehicle maintenance, and fuelling/charging) to third parties, potentially leading to cost reduction.

Understanding shared mobility business models is essential for formulating effective strategies and policies. As the industry changes, it is important to regularly improve these models to meet the evolving needs of users and society.

3.2 Benefits and issues of Shared Mobility

This section provides an overview of the benefits and issues associated with NMS classified by different topics. Each subsection focuses on a specific aspect of shared mobility, providing a comprehensive understanding based on extensive research and insights from the experience of GEMINI partners. This section aims to provide readers with a comprehensive understanding of the complexities and potential benefits that come with shared mobility.

3.2.1 GHG Emissions, air pollution, and public health

Benefits

NMS are usually associated with the use of vehicles powered by green energies and greater utilisation of autonomous vehicles, as suggested by Hyland & Mahmassani (2020) and Kim et al. (2019). Moreover, they contribute to improving the accessibility to public transportation stations. For all those reasons, NMS promote the shift from private cars towards sustainable modes of transportation (Cohen & Kietzmann, 2014; Jang et al., 2020; Karbaumer & Metz, 2021).

NMS have been extensively studied for their impact on greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) and air pollution. These services contribute to mitigating GHG and air pollution by reducing the number of vehicles and using clean energy sources. By sharing a vehicle with others, the need for individual car ownership is reduced, resulting in lower overall emissions from the vehicle fleet. For example, Nijland & van Meerkerk (2017) found that car sharers emit between 240 and 390 kilograms less CO₂ per person annually. This reduction corresponds to approximately 13% to 18% of their total CO₂ emissions related to car ownership and usage. Moreover, the research conducted by Amatuni et al. (2020) provides insights into the effects of car sharing on GHG in San Francisco, Calgary, and the Netherlands. Their findings reveal that car sharing can lead to GHG emissions reductions ranging from 3% to 18%, depending on the geographical location.

Additionally, the environmental benefits of e-scooters are noteworthy due to their zero tailpipe emissions when powered by renewable electricity. By using e-scooters instead of private cars, air pollution can be reduced extensively, leading to improved air quality in urban areas. Moreover, by promoting the use of electric vehicles in NMS, the emissions of air pollutants like nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and particulate matter (PM) will be reduced, thereby improving local air quality, especially in urban areas where air pollution is a major concern (Moreau et al., 2020).

Many studies collectively underscore the substantial positive impact of NMS on reducing emissions, making them a valuable component of sustainable urban transportation systems. However, it is important to note that this topic is somewhat controversial in literature, as it will be further discussed below.

Issues

Although NMS are often acknowledged for their emission-reducing potential, some studies challenge the general opinion. For example, the study conducted by Moreau et al (2020) concluded that **the environmental impact of shared dockless e-scooters greatly depends on the mode of transportation they replace and the intensity of their use**. Besides, the study revealed that the environmental impact of the mode of transportation replaced by private e-scooter users is approximately 6% higher than that of shared dockless e-scooter users. They observed a higher frequency of car replacement among e-scooter owners compared to users of shared dockless e-scooters. That indicates that using private e-scooters typically is a more sustainable choice compared to shared dockless e-scooters. **The study mentions that private e-scooters have a longer lifespan due to better usage and reduced vandalism**. Additionally, private e-scooters do not need to be rebalanced by a van. Similarly, Felipe-Falgas (2022) found that a shift in transportation modes resulting from the introduction of shared e-mopeds and shared e-bicycles led to an increase in GHG. Conversely, shared bicycles and private e-scooters contributed to decreased GHG emissions. **The results indicate that the environmental impact of shared mobility is highly influenced by the mode of transportation that it replaces**. If it replaces public transportation, this can limit the overall emissions reduction potential. Therefore, the

effectiveness of NMS services as an environmentally friendly urban mobility solution may not always be guaranteed.

Moreover, it is essential to consider the impact of shared mobility on public health. **The mode of transportation replaced by NMS can significantly affect public health.** Active travel options such as walking and cycling may contribute to reducing congestion, GHG, and air pollution while also promoting better health through increased physical activity (Bourne et al., 2020; Castro et al., 2019). If NMS mostly replace active modes, individuals' health can be affected. The relationship between shared mobility, emissions reduction, and public health is thus complex and requires comprehensive research to understand the impact on urban sustainability and citizens' health.

Furthermore, it is important to note that the impact of shared mobility on car ownership and the automotive industry remains uncertain. A study conducted by McKinsey & Company (2017) revealed that a significant percentage of respondents in the United States still preferred driving their own cars over using ride-hailing apps. In a similar vein, a study by Kolleck (2021) found that the influence of car sharing on the desire to give up owning a car might not be substantial enough to explain reductions in car ownership rates. Additionally, Haustein (2021) did not find significant results when analysing changes in car ownership among car sharing users in Copenhagen (Denmark). In light of these findings, it becomes clear that **the relationship between shared mobility, emissions reduction, and public health is not straightforward and requires more in-depth investigation.**

3.2.2 Integration of NMS with the mobility ecosystem

Benefits

Few studies in scientific literature, such as the work of Karlsson et al. (2016) have explored the integration of transportation within an app. However, it is notable that the supply of NMS is becoming concentrated in MaaS apps. In 2022, the *Free Now* app (see [MaaS 2](#)) evolved into a “mobility super app”, integrating a wide range of transportation services, including public transportation, NMS like cars, scooters, bikes, and mopeds, as well as ride-hailing and taxi services. Currently, this app operates in nine markets across over 150 European cities. A This unified app empowers users to effortlessly access and pay for a diverse array of transportation options, providing a complete mobility solution. Similarly, the *Urbi* app (see [MaaS 3](#)) offers a variety of services, including the purchase of train tickets, airport shuttles and ferries, and booking a taxi, ride-hailing, car sharing, bike sharing, or moped scooter sharing. It also provides the convenience of locating and utilising electric charging stations through the app. Users have the option to buy various packages or vouchers that combine different mobility services available on the app. It is accessible in 23 cities across Belgium, Italy, Spain, Germany, the Netherlands, and Austria (Kao et al., 2019). In this context, Mobility Service Providers (MSPs) play a pivotal role in expanding their services to incorporate these integrated apps, thereby enhancing the overall user experience.

Additionally, several other apps have been mentioned by project partners. One such app is *Whim* (see [MaaS 1](#), [MaaS 4](#), [MaaS 6](#) and [MaaS 7](#)), which is available in Helsinki (Finland), Turku (Finland), Antwerp (Belgium), Vienna (Austria), West Midlands (UK), various cities in Switzerland, and Greater Tokyo (Japan). *Whim* is an all-in-one mobility app that integrates e-scooter sharing, e-hailing, bike sharing, car sharing, and public transportation services. The success of this app has been attributed to its user-friendly interface and comprehensive coverage. The *Floya* app (see [MaaS 6](#)), recently launched in Brussels (Belgium), combines various public transport options and

NMS. The *Meep* app operates across cities such as Lisbon (Portugal), several cities in Spain (Málaga, Valencia, Sevilla, Gijón, Oviedo), Malta, and Nicosia (Cyprus). It collaborates with public institutions, public transport operators, and private mobility companies to offer a wide range of mobility options. Finally, the *UbiGo* mobility app (see [MaaS 1](#) and [MaaS 7](#)) successfully integrates public transport, car sharing, rental car services, and taxis in one app, demonstrating **the feasibility of bundling mobility options into packages, especially via subscriptions, to enhance user acceptance**. The company started operations in Stockholm in 2019.

This trend of integrating multiple NMS within a single app significantly contributes to the advancement of Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) and offers users greater convenience and flexibility in urban transportation.

Issues

Although digital platforms have made it easier to integrate NMS into MaaS applications, **there remains a significant challenge in ensuring harmonious coexistence between NMS and public transportation**. As indicated by some project partners in their case study templates (see [MaaS 2](#), [MaaS 3](#), [MaaS 4](#), and [MaaS 5](#)) there is still room for improvement in integrating NMS and public transportation from a fare and physical perspective. While MaaS succeeds at bringing various shared mobility options under a single app, coordinating NMS with traditional public transport requires further advancement. This represents an area where future research and development could lead to even more comprehensive and interconnected mobility solutions.

Furthermore, the aforementioned case studies have identified several challenges regarding the integration of NMS within the mobility ecosystem:

- Coordinating private-sector and public-sector stakeholders to build up an integrated system is often complex.
- MaaS apps are often too complex to use, particularly for people not familiar with technology. When users find it challenging to use or understand the system, the adoption rate can be low, and sometimes, the whole project or company might not succeed.
- Lack of technical integration and reliance to share data hinder an effective integration of mobility systems. When different transportation services cannot connect or work together well, the experience will be less enjoyable for users, particularly when switching between various modes of transportation. Therefore, achieving technological harmony is crucial to providing a user-friendly and effortless experience.

3.2.3 Cooperation between stakeholders and data sharing

Achieving effective collaboration among diverse shared mobility stakeholders can be challenging, particularly when it comes to facilitating seamless data sharing. Overcoming these challenges is vital because any difficulties encountered in collaboration can substantially affect the quality and performance of integrated services. To address these challenges, insights from the study by Polydoropoulou et al. (2020) can be valuable. This research aims to gain a deeper understanding of the motives, expectations, perceptions, and concerns of key stakeholders related to MaaS for the development of a more sustainable transportation system. The study applied a mixed-methods approach, including workshops with stakeholders and focus groups with end-users in Budapest and Greater Manchester, along with quantitative data gathered through an online survey. They identified several barriers to MaaS implementation, including the need for reorganisation of business by the MaaS actors, unwillingness to

cooperation between MSPs and MaaS operators, limited availability of APIs (Application Programming Interface), and unwillingness of transport operators to share data.

To address the challenges identified in the study conducted by Polydoropoulou et al. (2020) and to promote the successful implementation of MaaS, the following measures can be considered:

- Encouraging dialogue between transport operators and data providers to find mutually beneficial solutions.
- Establishing a regulatory framework to require or incentivise transport operators to willingly share pertinent data for MaaS implementation.
- Standardising data exchange protocols between MSPs and data providers to promote seamless integration.

These measures could contribute to the success of MaaS implementation and the achievement of its expected benefits, even though these measures will not be effective if mobility operators are not willing to share data.

3.2.4 Impact on traffic congestion and travel time

Benefits

One significant benefit of some forms of shared mobility is the potential to reduce travel time spent commuting (Machado et al., 2018). **Shared mobility is expected to alleviate traffic congestion** (Abduljabbar et al., 2021; Petit et al., 2023) as vehicles are usually smaller and shared among different users, contributing to travel time savings and reducing the stress associated with traffic. **The reduction in commuting time translates into overall productivity** as people spend less time stuck in traffic and more time engaged in productive activities, both at work and in their personal lives. This will have a positive impact on the economy and society as a whole (Carranza et al., 2016).

Notably, Drut (2018) highlights that **ridesharing significantly contributes to decreasing traffic congestion by increasing vehicle occupancy rates**. Through that approach, a single vehicle owned by the driver is offered to individuals to share travel costs. According to the author, short-distance trips typically have an average occupancy rate of 2.5 persons per car, while long-distance trips in France reach an average of 3.5 persons per car (1 driver plus 2.5 passengers). This higher occupancy rate results in a decreased need for vehicles to transport the same number of passengers.

Issues

However, **the impact of shared mobility on traffic congestion and travel time will ultimately depend on the availability and accessibility of NMS, as well as the mode of transportation being replaced**. Reck et al (2022) discuss substitution patterns of shared and personal micromobility. They explore the effects of shared bicycles, shared e-scooters, and other modes of transportation, such as public transit, private cars, and walking. The results suggest that personal e-bikes are used to replace trips across all four primary modes of transportation (walking, public transit, car, and biking). In contrast, shared e-bikes mostly substitute public transit and biking trips. **For short journeys, all micro-mobility modes predominantly replace walking, while for longer trips, they tend to replace public transport, biking, and cars**. Consequently, it is notable that the impact of shared mobility on congestion will be very sensitive to the modes that shared mobility substitutes.

Along the same line, Aguilera-García et al. (2021) found that the deployment of moped-sharing services in urban mobility has demonstrated positive effects on urban transportation by reducing the use of private vehicles, which has the potential to alleviate current problems of traffic congestion. However, the study also raised concerns about shared e-mopeds potentially capturing demand from public transit, which could affect the overall net impact of moped sharing on congestion and urban sustainability. In their most recent study, Aguilera-García et al. (2022) analysed the adoption and frequency of use of car sharing services in Munich (Germany) and Madrid (Spain) through a survey. The findings revealed that the sustainability impact of car sharing highly depended on the specific modes of transportation substituted. Based on the survey data, it was observed that public transit is the most affected mode, with 50% of car sharing users stating their intention to choose public transportation if car sharing services were not available. This clearly has negative consequences for traffic congestion.

3.2.5 Urban space optimisation

Benefits

Shared mobility enables more efficient use of resources as vehicles are utilised more intensively. Instead of having unutilised cars parked for most of the time, shared vehicles are in use for a longer duration, **maximising the utilisation of existing resources and reducing the need for space devoted to parking.** One interesting observation is that, on average, a car is estimated to be parked for 95% of its time (Nagler, 2021).

NMS, such as e-scooters and e-bikes, require less space for parking compared to private vehicles. This frees up valuable urban space that can be utilised for other purposes like parks, pedestrian zones, or bike lanes, contributing to a more sustainable urban environment. By reducing the need for private car ownership, these services create opportunities to repurpose public spaces for cycling lanes, pedestrian areas, and public transport (Boer et al., 2022; Karbaumer & Metz, 2021; [Carsharing 5](#)).

Issues

One of the problems of shared mobility concerning the occupation of space is that if regulation is not suitable, **free-floating vehicles may invade the sidewalks of the streets**, especially around transit stations. That situation may produce pedestrian bottlenecks that hinder the movement of people on the streets.

The impact of NMS on public infrastructure and space utilisation, including roads, sidewalks, and parking facilities, has raised important regulatory questions. Different cities have taken varied approaches to address these concerns. For instance, e-scooters are permitted on sidewalks or bicycle lanes in cities like Singapore (Che et al., 2020) and Brisbane (Haworth et al., 2021), under certain restrictions such as speed limit and the give-way rules. Conversely, in some countries such as Spain, riding e-scooters on sidewalks is still strictly forbidden primarily due to safety concerns (Sobrino et al., 2023).

3.2.6 Economic impacts

Using shared mobility is expected to have positive impacts on economic efficiency. One of its main advantages is **making mobility more cost-efficient through sharing vehicles and rides** (see [MaaS 2](#)). By utilising NMS, individuals can reduce their transportation expenses, particularly the ones coming from vehicle ownership, leading to significant savings in terms of vehicle purchase, maintenance, and insurance costs (Amatuni et al., 2020; Boer et al., 2022; da Silva et

al., 2023; Shaheen et al., 2019). This, in turn, allows people to release a share of their budget to other goods and services. **It is important to highlight that the economic efficiency impacts depend on the mode that is being replaced since public transportation is in most cases more cost-efficient than shared mobility.**

Shared mobility can also have a positive impact on the local economy by creating employment opportunities, especially in the case of services that hire drivers on a flexible, on-demand basis (Boer et al., 2022). This is particularly beneficial for those people seeking part-time or supplementary employment. **Given the technological complexity of NMS, they also promote knowledge-based jobs requiring high qualifications.**

Moreover, the innovation brought by NMS plays a crucial role in shaping economic impacts. For instance, Maas (2022) conducted a literature review on MaaS and emphasised the importance of interoperability through a universal programming interface, allowing devices, sensors, and users to access mobility services via a platform. This aligns with the findings of Oladimeji et al. (2023), which explore various technologies in intelligent transport systems, including IoT, communication protocols, and Service-Oriented Architecture systems. The study delves into the opportunities and challenges associated with deploying these technologies, fostering innovation in smart transportation. Furthermore, Jardim-Goncalves et al. (2020) present essential features and trends for the development of future MaaS systems, emphasising sustainability, digital transformation, and the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology. The study stresses the importance of mobility apps/platforms, calling for a cultural shift in awareness and proposing case studies as benchmarks for defining crucial functionalities.

The economic impacts of shared mobility extend beyond immediate cost savings, incorporating the transformative effects of innovation brought by MaaS and NMS. These innovations not only enhance economic efficiency but also contribute to the development of a dynamic mobility ecosystem.

3.2.7 Accessibility to resources and services

Benefits

Shared mobility can facilitate access to underutilised resources (Täuscher & Kietzmann, 2017). Extensive studies corroborate that collaborative consumption promotes social innovation (Hamari et al., 2016; Małecka et al., 2022; Piscicelli et al., 2015; Sanvicente et al., 2020). According to Wang et al. (2022), shared mobility represents a significant social innovation with the potential to transform urban transportation and how people interact with transportation systems.

One of the most notable impacts of shared mobility is its ability to enhance accessibility to transportation, especially for people living in areas with limited public transportation options. NMS can fill transportation gaps by **providing solutions to those without access to private vehicles or reliable public transit.** This access can significantly improve the quality of life for people living in areas with limited access to traditional transportation networks.

According to the study conducted by Lagadic et al. (2019), the development of Peer to Peer (P2P) car sharing services presents a potential solution for areas where demand is low. Therefore, **shared mobility models play a crucial role not only in improving accessibility to public transportation but also in addressing the challenges associated with their expansion into peri-urban regions.**

Issues

The challenge faced by NMS when expanding beyond central urban areas is noteworthy. Often, **it is difficult to find the necessary conditions for success in peri-urban areas, where such services are more necessary to provide accessibility to public transportation stations.** The development of infrastructure in these areas can be costly, and operators may find it challenging to justify the investment due to low demand. Moreover, the use of vehicles is often low in the peripheral areas, so operators rarely want to expand their business beyond city centres.

3.2.8 Social inclusion

Benefits

in the context of social inclusion, the SHARE-North project, funded by the European Union and investigated by Karbaumer & Metz (2021) explores the concept of shared mobility and its potential to address diverse needs and challenges across global, regional, and local contexts. One key finding from this research is **the role of shared mobility in fostering a sense of community and shared responsibility.** For instance, community-based ridesharing encourages neighbours to share rides with people travelling in the same direction. This not only helps build social connections but also reduces the environmental impact of individual trips (see [MaaC](#)).

The impacts of community-based shared mobility are still being studied. However, it has been observed to have a significant positive impact on social inclusion and neighbourhood cohesion, as participants become part of a social group (see [Carsharing 3](#)). Some notable examples of community-based car sharing initiatives include *CozyCar* in Belgium and *OnzeAuto* in the Netherlands (see [Carsharing 2](#)).

Moreover, **NMS can be transformative for individuals with disabilities.** One notable example of this can be found in the case study of *AvIRA Wheelchair-Friendly Carsharing*, as highlighted in Karbaumer & Metz (2021). This case study describes how a care centre for people with disabilities implemented shared mobility with wheelchair-accessible vehicles. It is worth noting that these specific vehicles are often underutilised so sharing them with other people with disabilities and neighbours can optimise their use. An additional example is *Wheeliz*, a platform in France that facilitates the sharing of wheelchair-accessible vehicles. This platform enables car owners to offer their adapted vehicles for rent to people with special needs.

These initiatives promote the social inclusion of individuals with reduced mobility by bringing them into closer contact with others in their neighbourhood.

Issues

The success of NMS largely depends on the convenience, willingness, and capacity of travellers to use the services offered to them. In this respect, the **dependence on the technology of NMS raises concerns about accessibility and equity** within these services and requires careful consideration from the user's perspective. Many research works have analysed the risk that NMS may exclude certain population groups due to limited technological capabilities. This notably affects individuals with lower incomes and older adults who may lack the necessary technological skills or access to electronic devices (Shaheen et al., 2017).

Moreover, it is important to acknowledge that **the high cost of NMS can be a limiting factor**, as noted by Shaheen & Cohen (2019). Individuals with lower incomes may perceive these services as costly. By offering discounts or subsidies to eligible low-income individuals, this challenge can be addressed, making NMS more financially accessible to a wider range of the population.

Despite that, **some shared mobility operators are reluctant to offer their services in less wealthy highly conflictive neighbourhoods** because of the risk of vandalism.

In addition, **concerns regarding digital exclusion have been raised**. While some public transit riders prefer cash payments, on-demand NMS usually require the use of credit cards or bank accounts, excluding users without access to traditional financial services (Pan & Shaheen, 2021). Moreover, mobile applications for shared mobility often require vehicle reservations, which might exclude certain individuals from utilising the service, particularly those without smartphones or those who face challenges with mobile technology. In contrast, some services like *Cambio* (a Belgian-German car sharing service) offer users the flexibility to book a vehicle either through their phone or the *Cambio* website (see [Carsharing 5](#)). These issues highlight the importance of considering various user needs and technological capabilities to ensure inclusivity in NMS utilisation.

Wang et al. (2022) suggest that **transit agencies could address the needs of less technology-savvy individuals by offering phone call and text options**, and by building smart kiosks in low-income and elderly neighbourhoods to enhance access to on-demand shared services. These agencies would serve as intermediaries between the users and the service providers. They would provide support in the form of education, training, and assistance in setting up accounts, making reservations, and understanding the available options. The aim is to ensure that individuals who may be less familiar with technology or face other challenges can still benefit from on-demand NMS. These agencies would play a crucial role in promoting equity and inclusivity in the adoption and use of these services, particularly for low-income individuals and older users who may be more vulnerable to technological barriers.

Ensuring that NMS are inclusive for all members of society, including those with limited technological capabilities, is critical. By addressing these challenges and promoting inclusivity, the shared mobility industry can move closer to realising its full potential in creating more accessible and equitable transportation systems for everyone.

3.2.9 Financial viability

One of the main challenges faced by shared mobility companies is the fact that the market is still relatively new and evolving, and there is no universal formula for success, **making it difficult for new players to develop models that ensure sustainable revenue sources**. Companies need to figure out how to turn the shared mobility concept into a profitable long-term venture. Finding a strong and adaptable business model is an ongoing priority for these service providers (Apte & Davis, 2019; Cohen & Kietzmann, 2014; Gilibert & Ribas, 2019; Lagadic et al., 2019; Täuscher & Kietzmann, 2017). Furthermore, another significant aspect arises in the process of developing shared mobility business models. Some MaaS platforms may find it difficult to align broader societal goals, especially if they prioritise profit over sustainability. Balancing economic viability with sustainability objectives presents a complex challenge (see [MaaS 6](#) and [MaaS 8](#)).

Some studies highlight the challenge of achieving profitability in shared mobility business models. For car sharing services, Lagadic et al. (2019) concluded that one of their greater challenges to ensure is the **instability and competitiveness in a market with a high number of new entrants**. This fact, along with a relatively small client base and a limited number of trips, makes it difficult for operators to generate sufficient revenue. Moreover, car sharing services often face the challenge of expanding their services beyond the central city as **it is difficult to find the necessary conditions for success in peri-urban areas, where their services would be**

more valuable to provide accessibility to public transportation stations. Developing their own infrastructure in these areas can be costly, and operators may struggle to justify the investment since the demand may be lower.

Potential collaborative opportunities exist between app-based car-related NMS, which can contribute to the creation of more profitable business models. However, the profitability of these services is influenced by several factors, including service fees, pricing strategies, and the targeted customer segments (Gilibert & Ribas, 2019).

Many shared mobility companies have struggled to achieve profitability due to high operating costs, low margins, intense competition, technological and regulatory challenges. Täuscher & Kietzmann (2017) analysed some failed companies in the sharing economy. For instance, *Sidecar* was a ride-sharing company that operated in the United States from 2011 to 2015. Despite being one of the first ridesharing companies to enter the market, *Sidecar* was acquired by General Motors in 2016 after facing tough competition from larger competitors like *Uber* and *Lyft*, which offered sign-up bonuses to attract new drivers and passengers. One of the main reasons for *Sidecar*'s failure was its inability to attract a critical mass of drivers and passengers, which limited its ability to provide reliable and convenient service.

Another example analysed by Täuscher & Kietzmann (2017) was *Carpooling.com*, a German firm founded in 2005, which was a pioneer and dominant player in the P2P carpooling market in Europe. The company provided a platform for car drivers to find co-passengers and share costs when travelling between cities. However, in 2013, *Carpooling.com* introduced a revenue model that charged participants a small commission fee for rides organised through its platform. This change, along with the requirement for upfront payment, was met with resistance from customers who were used to paying drivers in person after the ride. As a result, many users started using alternative carpooling sites, leading to a decrease in passengers and subsequently a decline in driver participation. As a result, the company lost a significant portion of its network, and in 2015, it was acquired by French competitor *BlaBlaCar*. Curiously, *BlaBlaCar* implemented a service fee years later when the business was already consolidated.

Additionally, the failed bike sharing company *Ofo* serves as another example of the challenges faced by shared mobility providers. The bankruptcy of *Ofo* was primarily attributed to aggressive and unsustainable expansion, poor financial management, intense competition, ineffective management of the shared bike fleet and the inability to maintain and repair the bikes (J. Ma, 2020).

3.2.10 Safety and security

One of the main safety concerns in shared micromobility is the risk of accidents (see [Micromobility 2](#) and [Ridesharing 2](#)). The literature on accidents in shared micromobility has been increasing in the past few years. For example, Osti et al. (2023) conducted an analysis of injury patterns of users of e-scooters and e-bikes in an inner-city trauma centre located in upper Manhattan. The study included 117 patients who were admitted to this trauma centre due to injuries sustained while utilising e-scooters or e-bikes. Among these patients, 75% were injured while riding e-scooters, 20% were injured while riding e-bikes, and 5% were injured while riding as a back rider on a scooter or as a pedestrian hit by a scooter. The findings of this research indicate that **e-bikes and e-scooters are associated with notable levels of injury severity**. The study suggests a need to review public policy regarding e-scooter and e-bike use regulations. This includes the enforcement of laws against driving while intoxicated, the implementation of

mandatory helmet regulations, educational initiatives, speed control measures, and the creation of special lanes and car-free zones.

Along the same line, Hanna et al. (2023) analysed the injury patterns associated with the use of e-scooters in the USA. The study aimed to identify the types of injuries sustained by patients hospitalised due to e-scooter incidents from 2015 to 2019. The study found that **hospital admissions due to e-scooter-related accidents more than doubled between 2018 and 2019**, with facial and skull fractures being the most frequently observed injuries. The lack of helmet usage was identified as a major contributing factor to these injuries. The authors recommend that states establish a standardised set of regulations for e-scooters, which should include minimum age requirements, helmet laws, and driver's license requirements.

Going beyond accident-related safety concerns, **security is another critical aspect of shared mobility**. However, there are only a few studies on this topic. For example, Acheapong (2021) explored passengers' perceptions and experiences regarding safety and security while using ride-hailing services in Accra and Kumasi (Ghana). This research aimed to identify factors that contribute to passengers' sense of safety and security during ride-hailing trips. To that end, the author conducted a survey between May and August 2019, targeting both users and non-users of internet-based ride-hailing platforms. The study highlighted seven key factors that impact safety and security in ride-hailing services: (i) the identification of drivers and vehicles before boarding; (ii) trackability (the ability for passengers to track their trips in real-time or share the trip with others) and traceability (the ability to trace personal belongings lost during a ride-hailing trip); (iii) exposure to malicious and criminal activities during ride-hailing trips; (iv) privacy concerns and travelling alone; (v) trust in the security features of ride-hailing apps; (vi) emergency use as an alternative in regions with limited ambulance services; and (vii) driver behaviour.

Addressing the issue of cybersecurity in NMS, Haas and Moller (2017) emphasise the need to safeguard car sharing services. Car sharing relies on a direct link between the vehicle and backend servers, facilitated by a GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication) connection. If this connectivity is disrupted by a denial-of-service attack or the vehicle's internal system is hacked to gain access to critical internal systems, it could have severe consequences. To mitigate these risks, the authors propose a combination of cybersecurity measures. One such measure is the use of encryption to ensure that all communication between the vehicle and the external world remains confidential. Additionally, they suggest implementing intrusion detection systems (IDS) to filter data streams from the connected vehicle and detect potential attacks. **Another crucial recommendation is to enforce strong authentication protocols between the vehicle, backend servers, and IoT devices**, such as Public-Private Key Infrastructures (PKI), Trusted Platform Modules (TPM), OpenAuth 2.0 authentication, and pre-shared keys with a challenge-response protocol and symmetric encryption.

In summary, addressing both safety concerns and cybersecurity issues is essential to ensure that NMS can provide their benefits securely, protecting both data integrity and passenger well-being.

3.2.11 Regulatory aspects

The fast adoption of shared mobility modes in urban areas worldwide has brought the need for regulatory frameworks to support these new mobility modes (Boer et al., 2022). However, **legal and regulatory frameworks have frequently struggled to keep up with the rapid development**

of these innovative services. This lag in regulation affects the public interest, the sustainable urban transit, efficiency, and inclusiveness of NMS (Machado et al., 2018; Sareen et al., 2021).

As NMS have continued to advance, regulatory agencies have found themselves racing to adapt their approach to managing this dynamic sector which includes public transport, and motorised and non-motorised modes. In this process, local authorities have emerged as key players in defining a regulatory framework for shared mobility. The challenges of regulating NMS in urban areas are further intensified by the need for effective management of public spaces (see [Micromobility 2](#)). **The dynamic nature of shared mobility requires regulations that are promptly adapted to each context.**

Moreover, **the emergence of shared mobility has disrupted traditional transportation markets and raised questions related to competition and market regulation.** It is widely known that traditional taxi services have experienced substantial challenges and disruptions from ride-hailing platforms (Lukasiewicz et al., 2022; Q. Ma et al., 2019; Su & Fang, 2019). It is essential to establish clear regulations and guidelines to ensure fair competition and protect the interests of all stakeholders involved in shared mobility.

This regulatory lag is a substantial impediment to realising the full potential of shared mobility. Bridging the regulatory gap is critical to reaping the numerous benefits of these new services.

In addition to these regulatory challenges, data sharing in MaaS is a critical aspect that involves the collection, processing, and data exchange among various stakeholders, including mobility providers, transportation authorities, and end-users (Cottrill, 2020). **One major concern related to data sharing is user privacy** with users expressing concerns on the security of their personal data, especially the exchange of tracking and credit card data (Polydoropoulou et al., 2020).

To address these concerns and promote secure data-sharing practices in MaaS, significant regulations have been established, such as the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). GDPR is a privacy regulation that sets stringent guidelines for the collection and processing of personal data. It provides users with greater control over their personal data and requires organisations to implement robust data security measures (General Data Protection Regulation, 2016). It is important to focus on understanding how technological and policy measures can be used to follow the changing rules and make users feel confident about how their data is handled. Since there are different interests involved in MaaS, it will be crucial to deal with privacy concerns and GDPR compliance from the beginning. All parties should utilise clear and adaptable methods that are transparently communicated to users (Cottrill, 2020).

3.3 Summary of benefits, issues, and challenges of Shared Mobility

The following table summarises the main benefits, issues and challenges of NMS found in the literature review undertaken in the previous Section.

TABLE 2 Summary of benefits, issues, and challenges of Shared Mobility

TOPIC	BENEFITS OF SHARED MOBILITY SERVICES (NMS)	ISSUES / CHALLENGES OF SHARED MOBILITY SERVICES
GHG Emissions, air pollution, and public health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NMS mostly use cleaner vehicles (electric, etc.) NMS make more intensive use of vehicles Some NMS promote a greater occupation of vehicles (ridesharing) Maas provides route optimisation and emissions information to users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not favorable if NMS mostly substitute active modes and mass public transit Shorter life cycle of shared vehicles (vandalism, lack of care by users) → larger emissions in the manufacturing phase
Impact on traffic congestion and travel time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many NMS use smaller vehicles Some NMS promote a greater occupation of the vehicles (ridesharing) Users have more alternatives to save travel time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not favorable if NMS mostly substitute active modes and mass public transit
Urban space optimisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smaller vehicles occupy less space More intensive use of the vehicles release public and private parking space for other purposes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occupation of space in sidewalks by free-floating vehicles
Accessibility to resources and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NMS facilitate access to underutilised vehicles NMS may help provide accessibility to transit stations in low-density areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NMS usually concentrate in city centres as they are usually not profitable in peri-urban areas
Social inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some NMS, such as MaaS or ridesharing, foster a sense of community and shared responsibility NMS can be transformative for individuals with disabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital exclusion High prices of NMS exclude poor people Sometimes NMS are not supplied in poor neighborhoods because of vandalism
Safety and Security		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some vehicles, such as shared e-bikes and e-scooters, are associated with notable levels of injury severity

TOPIC	BENEFITS OF SHARED MOBILITY SERVICES (NMS)	ISSUES / CHALLENGES OF SHARED MOBILITY SERVICES
Integration with the mobility ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> App-based services can be easily integrated thorough MaaS platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of NMS and public transport has proved to be difficult
Cooperation between stakeholders and data sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> App-based services produce a lot of data to share 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NMS operators are not willing to cooperate if that may affect their business performance NMS operators are reluctant to share data Technological systems are not always interoperable Data protection regulation constrains the possibility of sharing data
Regulatory aspects		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulation usually lags behind the development of NMS The dynamic nature of shared mobility requires regulations that are promptly adapted to innovation Authorities lack experience and knowledge of NMS market regulation (number of operators, data sharing requirements, etc.)
Economic impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sharing vehicles and rides makes mobility more cost-efficient compared to private use NMS create innovative jobs and enhance technological innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not favorable if NMS mostly substitute active modes and mass public transit
Financial viability		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High market instability and competitiveness with a large number of new entrants High regulatory uncertainty Difficult to ensure sustainable revenue sources

4 IDENTIFYING KEY DRIVERS FOR THE DESIGN OF GEMINI BUSINESS MODELS

This section identifies and prioritises the key drivers that need to be considered in the proper design of NMS business models. First, a descriptive analysis of the online survey conducted to identify and prioritise key drivers is presented. Then, the following subsections present the results of the survey concerning key societal goals, social innovation drivers and technical innovation drivers. A summary of the survey results has been published in the project [website](#).

4.1 Descriptive analysis of the survey

The online survey was conducted between September 27 and October 26, 2023. It was shared among the GEMINI partners and disseminated through the project dissemination channels ([LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#), and [website](#)) and other channels. The target stakeholders were government and regulations bodies, infrastructure managers and providers, mobility operators, ancillary services of mobility services, investors, financial institutions and insurance, and other stakeholders such as researchers, think tanks, consultancy firms, transport and user associations, urban planners, and smart city initiatives. The survey was successful and achieved 280 responses, of which 195 were complete and valid. The rest of the responses were not included in the analysis.

To differentiate opinions among the different types of NMS stakeholders answering the survey, respondents were asked to indicate the activity of the organisation they work for. For this purpose, six main categories with different subcategories were established: (i) Government and Regulation Bodies; (ii) Infrastructure Managers and Providers; (iii) Mobility Operators; (iv) Ancillary Services of Mobility Services; (v) Investors, Financial Institutions and Insurance; and (vi) Others, with Research and Academia being one of the subcategories.¹ Respondents were allowed to choose more than one category to describe their professional background. For instance, they were allowed to be defined as: "Government and Regulation Bodies" and "Infrastructure Manager and Providers". Thus, one organisation may be included in one or more of the aforementioned categories.

FIGURE 1 shows the composition of the sample according to the type of stakeholder of the respondents. Of those who responded "Others", the most common categories were "Consultancy firm" with 31 responses, "Smart city initiatives" with 27 responses, and "Urban planners" with 21 responses.

¹ Please see [Appendix KK](#) for a detailed breakdown of the subcategories considered.

FIGURE 1 Respondents categorised by type of stakeholder

To facilitate the understanding of the above figure, the percentage of respondents who chose each of the categories has been calculated. That is, 53% of the respondents worked for a government or regulatory body.

Regarding the professional background of the respondents, most of them work in large organisations (with 250 employees or more). That fact may explain why the scope of activity of 49% of the organisations is international. Regarding their working experience, respondents have an average of 14.6 years of experience with a standard deviation of 11.5 years.

FIGURE 2 Size of company, organisation, or government

FIGURE 3 Scope of business

It is important to acknowledge the dissemination work conducted by GEMINI partners since only 39% of respondents work in organisations or companies that are part of the consortium (see FIGURE 4 below).

FIGURE 4 Participation of the GEMINI consortium in the survey results

Respondents were also characterised according to their level of expertise in NMS and the extent to which they use NMS in their travel routine. This allows to know whether their answers are based solely on conceptual/professional knowledge of NMS, or whether they also reflect their experience with these mobility services.

FIGURE 5 shows that 59% of respondents consider themselves experts in NMS, while 23% consider they are not. On the other hand, FIGURE 6 indicates that 45% of respondents use NMS at least once per month –with only 3% using NMS on a daily basis– and 55% use them rarely or just every once in a while.

FIGURE 5 Extent to which respondents consider themselves experts in NMS

FIGURE 6 Respondents' frequency of use of NMS

Respondents were also asked to indicate the types of NMS they use from a list defined in the survey and to specify other NMS they use in case they were not included in the list. They reported using different types of NMS (see FIGURE 7 below), with the most widely used being shared micro-mobility –especially bike sharing (51%) and, to a lesser extent, kick scooter sharing (18%), and moped scooter sharing (11%). Car sharing was also widely used (41%). Ride-hailing and ridesharing services are also used although to a lesser extent. Services and infrastructure to integrate different NMS, such as MaaS and Mobility Hubs, have a relatively low usage among respondents, only 13% and 12% of respondents reported using them. Finally, 3% of respondents stated using other NMS, such as boat sharing and automated vehicles.

FIGURE 7 NMS used by respondents

4.2 Key societal/sustainability goals to tackle

This section aims to identify and prioritise key societal goals for social development and the extent to which NMS can contribute to achieving them. Through a literature review and in collaboration with the project consortium, key societal goals that NMS are likely to improve were identified. Subsequently, these goals were split into the three pillars of sustainability: **economic**, **social**, and **environmental** goals.

- **Economic goals:** (i) Financial sustainability of governments and businesses; (ii) Resiliency; (iii) Keeping prices of essential services at an affordable level; (iv) Job creation; (v) Promotion of innovation; and (vi) Productivity gains stemming from reducing congestion and bottlenecks.
- **Social goals:** (i) Accessibility for people with reduced mobility; (ii) Accessibility and proximity to goods and services; (iii) Gender equality; (iv) Social equity; (v) Health improvement; (vi) Education and training; (vii) Safety and security; (viii) Promoting work-life balance; (ix) Better use of public space in the cities; and (x) Quality of jobs.
- **Environmental goals:** (i) Mitigate climate change; (ii) Improve air quality in cities; (iii) Reduce noise pollution; (iv) Reduce energy consumption; (v) Reduce natural resources consumption; (vi) Promote circular economy; and (vii) Preservation of Ecosystem / Biodiversity

In the survey, respondents were provided with the list of key societal goals and asked two questions:

- 1) the general importance for society of each key societal goal (on a 5-point scale ranging from *Not important* to *Extremely important*); and
- 2) the level of contribution of NMS to achieving each key societal goal (on a 5-point scale ranging from *Nothing* to *Very much*).

As for the key societal goals under the fourth pillar of sustainability, **governance**, a similar process was followed for their identification: (i) Transparency; (ii) Democracy; (iii) Institutional Quality; (iv) Legal certainty; and (v) Justice. In the survey, respondents were then provided with the list of key governance goals and asked to rate the importance of each goal for the successful implementation of NMS (on a 5-point scale ranging from *Nothing* to *Very much*).

The level of importance and contribution was calculated by assigning to each response the numeric values shown in TABLE 3 below:

TABLE 3 Numerical and categorical levels.

Numerical level	Categorical level		
	Importance for society	Contribution of NMS to achieving key societal goals	Importance for successful NMS' implementation
1	Not important	Nothing	Not important
2	Slightly important	Little	Slightly important
3	Somewhat important	Something	Somewhat important
4	Very important	Much	Very important
5	Extremely important	Very Much	Extremely important

The following subsections are as follows. First, the results regarding key economic, social and environmental goals are presented. This is followed by a cross-sectional analysis of the questions to compare the importance of the three aforementioned key sustainability goals and understand how much potential NMS have to contribute to each of these goals. Finally, the results relating to the governance goals are presented.

4.2.1 Key economic goals

FIGURE 8 shows the respondents’ opinions concerning the **key economic goals’ importance for society**. The goals are sorted from the most to the least important. According to the survey, the most important ones are “Keeping prices of essential services at an affordable level”, “Financial sustainability to government and businesses” and “Resiliency”.

FIGURE 8 Level of importance to society of key economic goals

In its turn, FIGURE 9 shows the opinion of the respondents concerning **the potential contribution of NMS to promote key economic goals** sorted from highest to lowest potential. The “Promotion of Innovation” and “Productivity gains from reducing congestion” are considered to be the goals to which NMS can contribute the most. However, as shown in FIGURE 8, these goals are not considered of great importance for society. These results suggest that there is little alignment between the importance of key economic goals and the contribution of NMS to improving them.

FIGURE 9 Potential contribution of NMS to achieving key economic goals

4.2.2 Key social goals

FIGURE 10 shows the opinion of the respondents concerning the **key social goals' importance for society** sorted from the most to the least important. It shows that the most important ones are: "Better use of public space in cities", "Safety and security", "Accessibility for people with reduced mobility" and "Accessibility and proximity to goods and services". On the other hand, the key goals that were found the least important were "Quality Jobs" and "Gender equality".

FIGURE 10 Level of importance to society of key social goals

In its turn, FIGURE 11 shows the opinion of the respondents concerning **the potential contribution of NMS to achieve key social goals** sorted from highest to lowest potential. The “*Better use of public space in the cities*” and “*Accessibility and proximity to good and services*” are considered to be the goals to which NMS can contribute the most. The key goals towards which NMS can contribute the least were “*Quality Jobs*” and “*Gender equality*”, which also happen to be of relatively little importance for society.

Thus, for key social goals, there seems to be greater alignment between their importance for society and the contribution of NMS to improving them except for the case of “*Safety and Security*”. Although this key goal is considered the second most important for society, respondents consider that NMS can contribute little to its improvement.

FIGURE 11 Potential contribution of NMS to achieving key social goals

4.2.3 Key environmental goals

FIGURE 12 shows the opinion of the respondents concerning the **key environmental goals’ importance for society** sorted from the most to the least important. Overall, respondents consider that environmental criteria are very important for society, “*Air quality in cities*” and “*Mitigation of Climate Change*” being the most important ones.

FIGURE 12 Level of importance to society of key environmental goals

FIGURE 13 shows the opinion of the respondents concerning **the potential contributions of NMS to promote key environmental-related goals** sorted from highest to lowest potential. In this case, the importance for society is fully aligned with the contribution of NMS to improve them, as “*Improve air quality in cities*” and “*Mitigation of Climate Change*” are considered the goals that NMS can improve the most.

FIGURE 13 Potential contribution of NMS to achieving key environmental goals

4.2.4 Cross-sectional analysis of economic, social, and environmental goals

To have a full picture of the impacts, a scatter plot was depicted to compare the importance of all key sustainability goals and understand the way NMS may contribute to such goals. The x-axis shows the importance of each goal for society, according to the opinions of respondents. The y-axis displays the potential contribution of NMS to such goals, according to the opinions of respondents. Control lines were drawn to show which key goals were above the mean score for each axis. Such lines divide the scatter plot graph into four quadrants. The upper right quadrant

shows the goals that are considered the most important ones for society and expected to be most positively influenced by NMS.

It is worth noting that the importance of the different goals is concentrated in a very narrow high range from 3.8 to 4.4, which shows that all goals are considered fairly important for society. The potential contribution of NMS to the achievement of those goals has a much greater variance, ranging from 2.5 to 4.

Economic		Environmental		Social	
ID	Key goals	ID	Key goals	ID	Key goals
1	Financial sustainability of governments and businesses	7	Improve air quality in cities	14	Accessibility and proximity to goods and services
2	Job creation	8	Mitigate climate change	15	Accessibility for people with PRM
3	Keeping prices of essential services at an affordable level	9	Preserve Ecosystem / Biodiversity	16	Better use of public space in the cities
4	Productivity gains stemming from reducing congestion and bottlenecks	10	Promote circular economy	17	Education and training
5	Promotion of innovation	11	Reduce energy consumption	18	Gender equality
6	Resiliency	12	Reduce natural resources consumption	19	Health improvement
		13	Reduce noise pollution	20	Promoting work-life balance
				21	Quality of jobs
				22	Safety and security
				23	Social equity

FIGURE 14 Cross-cutting analysis of the importance of key sustainability goals and the potential of NMS to contribute to their achievement

It is worth noting that all key goals located above the means (upper right quadrant) belong to the social and environmental categories. In the environmental category, the following key goals

stand out with their high ratings: "Improve air quality in cities", "Mitigate climate change", "Reduce energy consumption" and "Reduce natural resources consumption". In the social category, the key goals "Better use of public space", "Accessibility and proximity to goods and services", and "Accessibility for people with reduced mobility" stand out. Therefore, these are the key societal goals that are considered the most important ones for society and that NMS can contribute the most to achieve.

It should be noted that no key goal in the economic category is above average in terms of importance for society, though they are still important since, as was previously mentioned, the importance range is very narrow. However, there are two economic goals – "Productivity gains stemming from reducing congestion and bottlenecks" and "Promotion of Innovation" – that can be strongly influenced by NMS (two red dots located in the upper-left quadrant of the figure).

4.2.5 Key governance goals

FIGURE 15 shows the opinion of the respondents concerning the **key governance goals' importance for the successful implementation of NMS** sorted from the most to the least important. Overall, all governance-related goals are considered very important for the successful implementation of NMS (see FIGURE 15 below). However, **the highest scores for the successful implementation of NMS were given to "Legal certainty" and "Institutional Quality"**. This is an expected result since they are paramount to reducing the risk of implementing NMS.

FIGURE 15 Level of importance of governance goals for the successful implementation of NMS

4.3 Social innovation drivers

This section explores the importance of a set of social trends that may trigger innovations expected to transform society in the next few years. It also studies the potential impact that such social trends may have on boosting NMS. To that end, respondents were provided with a list of pre-identified social trends and asked in two separate questions to specify:

- 1) each social trend's current importance (on a 5-point scale ranging from *Not important* to *Extremely important*), and;
- 2) the extent to which each social trend can positively or negatively influence the adoption and frequency of use of NMS (on a 5-point scale ranging from *Negatively* to *Positively*).

The numerical average to determine the level of importance of social trends and their influence on NMS was calculated using the conversions shown in TABLE 4 below:

TABLE 4 Numerical and categorical levels

Numerical level	Categorical level	
	Importance of social trends nowadays	Influence of social trends in the use of NMS
1	Not important	Negatively
2	Slightly important	Somehow Negatively
3	Somewhat important	Nothing
4	Very important	Somehow Positively
5	Extremely important	Positively

After the first question, respondents were also asked to indicate in a blank space any social trend they considered important and was not reflected in the preconceived list.

FIGURE 16 shows the level of importance that respondents gave to the social trends sorted from the most to the least important. It can be observed that "Sustainability and environmental concerns", "Aging of the population", "Use of e-commerce" and "Working from home culture" are considered key social drivers nowadays.

FIGURE 16 Level of importance of social trends nowadays

FIGURE 17 shows the opinions of the respondents about the influence each social trend is expected to have in the adoption and frequency of use of NMS. Social trends have been sorted from most to least expected positive influence on NMS. The results highlight that the social trends that are expected to positively influence the adoption and frequency of use of NMS to a greater extent are "Detachment of car ownership", "Sustainability and environmental concerns" and "User's demand for a greater quality of service". It is observed that they are not necessarily associated with their level of importance for society according to the opinion of the respondents. For instance, while "Sustainability and environmental concerns" was rated as the most important social trend, "User's demand for a greater quality of service" and "Detachment of car ownership" fell in the middle of the list, ranking 6th and 9th respectively.

In addition, **it should be noted that "Aging of the population" is not only a social trend that is considered very important nowadays, but it is also expected to affect somehow negatively the adoption and frequency of use of NMS.** Thus, it should be considered a threat to the successful implementation of NMS. **The development of NMS business models should definitely consider the needs of the elderly if they want to gain potential in the future.**

FIGURE 17 Expected influence of social trends in the adoption and frequency of use of NMS

To have an overall view of the analysis, a scatter plot was depicted to compare all social trends and evaluate which are the most important for society currently (x-axis) and, at the same time, can positively or negatively influence the adoption and frequency of use of NMS (y-axis). Control axes were depicted to show which social trends are above and below the mean score for each variable, and to determine which social trends have the greatest potential to positively influence the adoption and frequency of use of NMS (upper right quadrant).

ID	Social trends	ID	Social trends
1	Aging of the population	8	Rural depopulation
2	Boom of tourism	9	Sustainability and environmental concerns
3	Detachment of car ownership	10	Urban sprawl
4	Digitalisation of relationships	11	Use of e-commerce
5	Immigration growth	12	Use of social networks
6	Increase of sustainable finance	13	User's demand for a greater quality of service
7	New family models	14	Working from home culture

FIGURE 18 Cross-cutting analysis of the importance of social trends nowadays and their influence on the use of NMS

The analysis indicates that "Detachment of car ownership", "Sustainability and environmental concerns", "User's demand for a greater quality of service" and "Working from home culture" are the current major social trends that are expected to positively influence the adoption and frequency of use of NMS to the greatest extent. Therefore, it is advisable to follow up on the development of those trends as they may be crucial to explain the successful implementation of NMS.

Also, 20 respondents (10% of the total) indicated in a blank space other social trends they considered important and were not explicitly mentioned in the survey, such as "politicisation" and "polarisation of opinions".

4.4 Technical innovation drivers

This section delves into the potential of new technologies and how they may benefit and enhance aspects necessary for the right implementation of NMS.

Considering the complexity of modern urban mobility, certain technological enablers may have a more profound impact on NMS, as well as the potential to become indispensable for their seamless operations and sustainability. Based on a literature review and the views of the consortium's business experts, key technical innovations or enablers were clustered into five main categories:

- **ICT and Physical Infrastructure:** The different physical or technological enablers in this category ensure the smooth and efficient functioning of (New) Mobility Services. These allow MaaS companies to provide, monitor and manage their fleet, thereby improving service reliability and enhancing the overall user experience.
- **Intelligent Systems & Decision-Making Solutions:** This category includes technologies or software solutions that leverage big data and AI techniques, from the data generated from the Mobility services users or other sources, for providing advanced analytics and fleet management capabilities. Thus, promoting operational optimisation and sustainability for operators and enhancing the overall service efficiency and profitability.
- **Cyber Security and Data Management:** This includes technologies, standards or software solutions for facilitating seamless data integration, interoperability, and semantic understanding among shared mobility actors and their digital systems. Additionally, these technologies protect user personal data and transactions, ensuring the secure and reliable functioning of NMS within the MaaS ecosystem.
- **Vehicle Connectivity Innovations:** Exemplified by V2I (Vehicle to Infrastructure) and V2V (Vehicle to Vehicle) communication technologies, these empower MaaS operators with real-time data facilitating dynamic route optimisation and fleet management. For example, self-driving cars and platooning concepts could lead to increased road safety and enable more streamlined, coordinated transportation services.
- **Alternative Power Solutions:** Embracing biodiesel, renewable diesel, natural gas, electric batteries and hydrogen fuel cells aligns with environmental and operational sustainability as well as reducing the carbon footprint of MaaS operations. Beyond environmental merits, these technologies have the potential to translate into lower operational costs, enhanced reliability, and a competitive edge in the market, positioning MaaS operators as pioneers both in technological and sustainable terms.

These factors and technologies are integral to the development and success of innovative NMS and business models. The distributed questionnaire went beyond the identification of key technical enablers, asking respondents about the impact of the adoption of such solutions and technologies, as well as barriers to their implementation such as regulatory frameworks, infrastructure availability and user acceptance. Particularly, respondents were asked to evaluate:

- the potential of a set of technology enablers to transform the current mobility landscape (in a 5-point scale ranging from *Very low potential* to *Very high potential*);
- the potential of a set of specific emerging technologies to boost innovative NMS (on a 5-point scale ranging from *Very low potential* to *Very high potential*); and
- the impact that emerging technologies may have on a set of mobility service-related attributes (on a 5-point scale ranging from *Very low impact* to *Very high impact*).

TABLE 5 below shows the categorical levels and associated numerical variables that were used in the questionnaire.

TABLE 5 Numerical and categorical levels for the importance of social trends

Numerical level	Potential levels	Impact levels
1	Very low potential	Very low impact
2	Low potential	Low impact
3	Moderate Potential	Moderate impact
4	High potential	High impact
5	Very high potential	Very high impact

Respondents were also asked to indicate:

- which NMS can benefit most from technological innovations from a list of NMS; and
- the greatest barriers/challenges to fostering the integration of technical innovations into NMS from a list of potential barriers/challenges.

In both cases, respondents were also asked to indicate in a blank space any barrier/challenge and NMS they considered important and were not reflected in the preconceived lists.

In the following subsections, the results obtained in each of the five aforementioned questions are presented.

4.4.1 Potential of technology enablers to transform the current mobility landscape

FIGURE 19 shows the opinions of the respondents on the potential that different technology enablers are expected to have in the transformation of the current global mobility landscape sorted from the most to the least expected potential.

Surprisingly, *“Physical and ICT infrastructure”* (such as charging infrastructure, dedicated lanes, mobility hubs, and wireless communication networks) stands out with the highest potential to change the current mobility landscape. Other technology enablers such as *“Intelligent systems and decision-making solutions”* (data visualisation tools and dashboards, fleet management software, analytics solutions, data mining, AI and machine learning) and *“Advanced vehicle technologies and solutions”* (vehicle connectivity, self-driving cars, and car platooning) are also considered important.

The latter underlines the fundamental role of strong physical and ICT infrastructures, the importance of decision-support technologies to enable efficient and informed mobility choices, and the need to implement technologies in vehicles to make them more efficient, safe, and accessible.

It is worth noting that *“Alternative power and energy solutions”* and *“Data security and management”* are not considered as important by respondents as might have initially been expected.

FIGURE 19 Potential of technology enablers to change the current mobility landscape.

4.4.2 Potential of specific emerging technologies to boost innovative NMS

FIGURE 20 shows the opinions of the respondents on the expected potential of specific emerging technologies to drive innovative NMS, ranked from the most to least expected potential.

The results show that the technologies that are expected to have the greatest potential to drive NMS innovation are "Advanced fleet monitoring and management solutions", "IoT infrastructure and smart cities", "Big Data, AI and machine learning techniques" and "Connected, cooperative and autonomous vehicles". It is worth highlighting that these technologies are aligned with the technology enablers with greater potential to transform the current mobility landscape described in [Section 4.4.1](#).

Such technologies are crucial to manage data in real time and to monitor and optimise the operational efficiency of NMS vehicles. They also enable integration and interconnected decision-making solutions across different players, which could improve the quality of NMS systems to attract and retain potential users.

FIGURE 20 Potential of emerging technologies to boost innovative NMS

4.4.3 Impact of technologies on specific service-related attributes of NMS

Regarding the potential impact of emerging new technologies on specific service-related attributes of NMS, FIGURE 21 shows that respondents consider that new technologies can contribute most to improving "Modal integration", "User experience, customer satisfaction, and quality of service", and "Accessibility and proximity of transport services to people". Thus, it can be inferred that the NMS that will benefit the most from innovative technologies will be those focused on mobility service integration, such as MaaS and Mobility Hubs.

In contrast, it seems that technology is not expected to have a major impact on important social goals such as "Affordability of services" and "Equity and Social Inclusion". As was already mentioned in [Section 3.2](#), this is one of the major issues of shared mobility services, which emerging technologies do not appear to solve.

FIGURE 21 Potential impact of technologies on specific service-related attributes of NMS

4.4.4 NMS benefiting most from technological innovations

FIGURE 22 shows the opinions of the respondents on which NMS are expected to benefit the most from technological innovations, ranked from the most to the least benefited. In this question, respondents were allowed to choose more than one NMS. Thus, to facilitate the understanding of the figure, the percentage of respondents who chose each NMS has been indicated. For instance, “MaaS” was found to benefit from technological innovations by 63% of respondents.

As expected from the results of the previous section, **respondents stated that the NMS that can benefit the most from innovative technologies is MaaS**, which allows access to different modes of transportation in an integrated manner. In addition, services such as mobility hubs that facilitate integration between different modes, and on-demand microtransit, show a high potential to benefit from technological innovations. It is worth noting that these two NMS were among those with the lowest level of use reported by respondents, so new technologies may be crucial in boosting the usage of those services in the next few years.

On the contrary, respondents believe that ride-hailing and **certain types of micromobility services**, such as moped scooter sharing and kick scooter sharing, **have little potential to benefit from technological innovations**.

FIGURE 22 NMS expected to benefit most from technical innovations

Finally, some respondents stated that autonomous vehicles and school transportation have the potential to benefit from technical innovations in a very important way.

4.4.5 Challenges in integrating of technical innovations into NMS

FIGURE 23 shows the respondents' opinions on the main challenges in promoting the integration of technical innovations in NMS, ranked from the most to the least important. In this question, respondents were allowed to choose more than one challenge. Thus, to facilitate the understanding of the figure below, the percentage of respondents who chose each challenge is indicated. For instance, "Regulator hurdles" was found to be a challenge by 70% of respondents.

Respondents considered "Regulatory hurdles" as the main challenge to promote the integration of technical innovations into NMS. It should be noted that this result is aligned with the most important key governance goal pointed out by the respondents for the proper implementation of NMS, "Legal certainty" (see [Section 4.2.5](#)). It is therefore considered one of the key aspects to work for promoting and guaranteeing the suitable operation of NMS.

FIGURE 23. Challenges to foster the integration of technical innovations into NMS

The second most important challenge is "infrastructure availability". This result is aligned with the importance that respondents gave to "Physical and ICT infrastructure" as a key technical driver to promote NMS and with the low usage of MaaS and Mobility Hubs reported by respondents in [Section 4.4.1](#).

The following four challenges in order of importance are: "Lack of political support/funding from local governments", "Concerns over sharing commercially sensitive data", "Lack of public awareness on key benefits" and "Lack of user adoption". These challenges still highlight the current difficulties of coordination and cooperation between key stakeholders when it comes to successfully implementing NMS, including effectively communicating their benefits to potential users. Improved communication could also have a positive impact on the adoption rate and frequency of use of NMS, which is another challenge faced by these services, thus facilitating their financial viability over time.

When asked about additional challenges not indicated in the survey, some interesting aspects pointed out by the respondents included the adoption of policies for transit reorganisation,

integration of NMS with public transport, and finding the right balance between the financial operation of NMS and the needs of users.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This section summarises the main conclusions regarding the benefits and challenges of NMS, their impact on key societal goals, and the emerging innovation drivers from the social and technical perspective that may affect NMS.

Regarding benefits and challenges of NMS:

- NMS are taking advantage of new information and communication technologies to bring about innovation to the mobility ecosystem. This is producing outstanding social benefits, but also prompting great challenges that need to be addressed to make mobility more sustainable in the future.
- The impact of NMS on environmental sustainability highly depends on the mode of transport it substitutes. In fact, many studies point out that a great share of modal substitution comes from active modes and public transportation. An important challenge is to promote NMS in those market niches where they do not compete, but rather cooperate, with mass public transport and active modes.
- NMS facilitate more rational use of mobility resources through sharing vehicles and rides. They also reduce the need for space devoted to parking. However, the shorter life cycle of shared vehicles due to vandalism and lack of care represents a great challenge for the life cycle assessment of vehicles.
- The impact of shared mobility on traffic congestion and travel time depends on the availability and accessibility of NMS, as well as the mode of transportation being replaced.
- NMS have the potential to provide greater capillarity to mass public transit stations in low-density areas located on the outskirts of the city. However, many NMS operators tend to limit their operation range to the city centre where services are more profitable, but where they usually substitute mass public transit and active modes such as walking.
- A seamless integration between mass public transit and NMS has not been achieved yet. That would require greater cooperation between public transport authorities and NMS in sharing data, developing infrastructure, and implementing integrated fare policies.
- Regarding inclusivity, NMS have great potential to widen the scope of mobility possibilities to disabled people. However, digital exclusion remains an issue. Additionally, the high prices of NMS and the fact that some shared mobility operators are reluctant to offer their services in less wealthy highly conflictive neighbourhoods compromise the inclusivity of NMS.
- Most NMS have not been able to provide a stable and sustainable source of funding given the great instability and competitiveness in the market, along with the uncertain regulation framework.
- Some NMS, especially micromobility, have proved to have high accident rates. Promoting regulations that may guarantee high safety standards for these NMS remains a challenge.
- Regulatory and legal aspects are considered the most important governance drivers to boost NMS. The dynamic nature of shared mobility requires regulations that are promptly adapted to each context.

Regarding the potential impact of NMS on key societal goals:

- NMS are expected to have the greatest sustainability impact on environmental and social goals, mainly air quality in cities, climate change mitigation, better use of public space in cities, and accessibility to goods and services.
- NMS are also expected to have a positive impact on economic goals, mainly the promotion of innovation and productivity resulting from reducing congestion. However, these goals are not considered as important for society as other economic goals that NMS barely influence such as keeping prices at an affordable level.

Regarding the emerging social and technical innovation drivers that may affect NMS:

- The main social trends that are expected to positively influence the adoption and frequency of use of NMS are sustainability and environmental concerns, use of e-commerce, and working from home culture.
- Aging of the population is not only a social trend that is currently considered very important but it is also expected to affect somehow negatively the adoption and frequency of use of NMS. The development of NMS business models should consider the needs of the elderly if they want to gain potential in the future.
- The specific technologies with the greatest potential to drive NMS innovation are advanced fleet monitoring and management solutions; IoT infrastructure and smart cities; Big Data, AI and machine learning techniques; and connected, cooperative and autonomous vehicles.
- Modal integration, customer satisfaction, and accessibility of transport to people are the service-related attributes that can benefit the most from the use of emerging technologies. In that framework, MaaS appears to be the specific NMS that is expected to take greater advantage of new technologies.
- Regulatory hurdles and the availability of infrastructure (physical and ICT) are considered the most important challenges to fostering the integration of technical innovation within NMS.

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APPENDIX A: TEMPLATE USED TO GATHER INFORMATION ON SHARED MOBILITY BUSINESS MODELS FROM GEMINI PARTNERS

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	
New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)	
<i>[Type of business model]</i>	
Brief Description of the BM	
<i>[Brief description of the business model implemented]</i>	
Case studies where the BM has been implemented	
<i>[Indicate where the BM has been deployed and description]</i>	
Successes	
<i>[Explain the main successes (scalability, network effects, efficiency gains, environmental advantages, political acceptance and support, integration with other transport modes, etc.)]</i>	
Obstacles or failures	
<i>[Explain the main obstacles/failures (lack of alignment between business and societal goals, limited space in urban areas, issues to coordinate different stakeholders, lack of communication between public authorities and mobility service providers, lack of acceptance or understanding by certain groups of users, lack of product-market fit, low affordability for the users, low transaction frequency, technological challenges, inability to attract venture capital, flaws in the organisational design, high competition, unexpected changes in legal environment, etc.)]</i>	
References	
<i>[Include references to articles, EU project deliverables, consultancy reports, etc. where the case study is discussed]</i>	

APPENDIX B: CARSHARING 1

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

GoodMoovs

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
One-way free floating car sharing in open communities
Brief Description of the BM
This model allows travellers to pick up and drop the car at any location within the service area.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
The public service “Autolib” was run by a private company, Bolloré. In 2018, the service had some 150,000 subscribers sharing nearly 4,000 vehicles in Paris and 103 surrounding cities. But after seven years, the service was not profitable, because the offer of electric vehicles couldn't satisfy user demand.
Successes
Wide availability leads to a decrease in car ownership in the service area. 6,000 dedicated chargers made it easy to charge a shared car.
Obstacles or failures
The operator faces a complex logistic challenge to maintain the fleet since the positioning of the cars is continuously subject to change. Moreover, fleet availability is essential for free-floating service providers and must be delivered by the car-sharing companies. Therefore, the demand imbalance between areas implies that vehicles must be relocated to maintain a certain service level in the entire service area. Free-floating system operators try to reduce the complexity of operations by stimulating users to refuel (or recharge) by offering discounts and by introducing dynamic pricing strategies to balance demand between areas. The cars are often left dirty and damaged, which increases maintenance costs. Additionally, the growing market of smaller electric vehicles, such as bikes and scooters, meant the car-sharing service was facing tough competition.
References
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://theicct.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/na-us-eu-ldv-electric-carsharing-factors-aug21_0.pdf

APPENDIX C: CARSHARING 2

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	GoodMoovs
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Two-way station-based car sharing in closed communities
Brief Description of the BM
<p>In comparison with one-way the two-way station-based model results in less, but longer reservations with higher kilometric and hourly revenues.</p> <p>Station-based car sharing services are mostly used to replace the usage of a private car, whereas one-way car sharing services offer an addition to the modal offer available in the area.</p> <p>Closed communities restrict the availability of shared cars to a limited number of users. These users share one or more cars together that are only available for this group of people.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
OnzeAuto.com is a sharing initiative that is locally driven and demand-driven.
Successes
<p>A car sharer at OnzeAuto knows the group of people who share the cars. Together, this group of people feels responsible that the cars stay clean, that the tire pressure is in order, and that new car-sharers receive a warm welcome. This way, the cars really feel like their own.</p> <p>For the car operator, this approach results in less damage and less support costs because the group prefers to support each other instead of calling a call centre to ask questions.</p>
Obstacles or failures
<p>There must be enough enthusiastic neighbours to start a new hub with shared cars.</p> <p>There has to be a charging facility available in the neighbourhood.</p>
References
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.onzeauto.com/

APPENDIX D: CARSHARING 3

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Forum Virium Helsinki
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)²
Business-to-consumer (B2C) car sharing for neighbourhoods or housing companies
Brief Description of the BM
Fleet of shared cars distributed to certain neighbourhoods or specific houses
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
Omago
Successes
It especially, and surprisingly, helps the construction business and real estate companies. Coupled with the house, it makes the house more attractive for sale. But, most importantly, in Finland, with one shared car with a long operation contract, it is allowed to build 5 fewer resident parking spots in new housing – leading to huge savings in construction costs.
Obstacles or failures
Does not meet the usual everyday demand of a car that also needs to be parked longer times somewhere else than home – the costly time of a shared car still makes an own car more favourable in many cases.
References
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://omago.fi/en/ • https://omago.fi/en/tenants-car/ • https://jyx.jyu.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/69975/1/URN%3ANBN%3Afi%3Aju-202006164208.pdf

² Only Finnish examples of companies and business models listed here by Forum Virium Helsinki. Most common international new mobility business models such as city bikes, shared cars (DriveNow, Green Mobility, etc.) and e-scoots (TIER, VOI, Lime etc) not included.

APPENDIX E: CARSHARING 4

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Forum Virium Helsinki
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Peer-to-peer car sharing
Brief Description of the BM
Private individuals sharing their private cars through online platforms (and services, including insurance, etc.)
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
BloxCar GoMore
Successes
GoMore has succeeded with the same business model that Finnish startup BloxCar had (but went bankrupt). Peer-to-peer car sharing has become well well-established, relatively well-known, professional, and non-risky way for customers to have cheap car rentals and car owners to earn some extra money from their cars.
Obstacles or failures
BloxCar was relatively popular in Finland but still bankrupted - as it might have been too labour-intensive and local, considering the cheap rentals on where to get their share. Managing this business profitability seems to need much automation and large scale. If one rental through the platform gets usually some 10-30 euros for the company, the company really needs thousands of rentals monthly to run any professional team behind it.
References
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://futuremobilityfinland.fi/member/blox-car-shared-cars-from-locals/ • https://pledgetimes.com/sharing-economy-bloxcar-which-provided-peer-to-peer-cars-went-bankrupt/

APPENDIX F: CARSHARING 5

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	European Passengers' Federation
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Business-to-Consumer (B2C) car sharing
Brief Description of the BM
A business owns a fleet of vehicles that can be rented out to their members, either by the minute, hour, or day.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>Poppy: a Belgian-based car sharing (and scooter sharing) application operating in four cities and three airports. Poppy has more than 750 cars in free-floating zones across the country, in addition to 2,000 kick scooters in Antwerp.</p> <p>Cambio: a Belgian-German car sharing service with more than 2,000 vehicles in more than 80 cities.</p>
Successes
<p>Efficient resource use: According to a 2018 study in Zurich, 18% of parking spaces used by private vehicles could be removed if all trips previously made by private cars were made by shared vehicles instead.</p> <p>Adaptability to user needs: Many car sharing services offer different types and sizes of vehicles, according to the user's needs. They also offer different subscriptions and pricing plans based on daily or occasional use. Unlike traditional car rentals that operate during business hours, car sharing allows users to access a car at any time of day. Lastly, vehicles are generally parked in various locations throughout a city, which makes accessing them more convenient.</p> <p>Cost saving: Owning a car costs money, even when it is not being used. Car sharing can reduce costs by allowing people to only pay when they need a car. For some applications, like Poppy, parking is free in a "Poppy zone".</p> <p>Less maintenance: Maintenance, cleaning, and insurance are generally covered by the car sharing company.</p>
Obstacles or failures
<p>Unclear terms of service: According to a 2019 study in Belgium, non-users were confused about different aspects of car sharing, such as costs and liability. Car sharing services each have their own subscription and pricing plans, which makes it difficult to compare between car sharing companies, but also makes it difficult to compare car sharing to owning a private vehicle.</p> <p>Limited availability: Car sharing services may not be available in all cities or regions, limiting access for potential users.</p> <p>Inclusivity aspects: Some car sharing services, like Poppy, require the user to download a mobile application to reserve a vehicle. This may cause some people to be excluded from using the service, such as people who do not have a smartphone, or people who have difficulties using mobile technologies. However, some other services, like Cambio, allow users to book a vehicle via the phone and the Cambio website.</p> <p>Travel and parking limitations: For some car sharing applications, like Poppy, it is forbidden to leave the country with a Poppy vehicle, or to park in an underground parking garage. Since the focus of car sharing is often on traveling shorter distances, this may dissuade some people from using the service.</p>
References
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- <https://poppy.be/en>
- <https://www.cambio.be/nl-vla>

APPENDIX G: CARSHARING 6

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

European Passengers' Federation

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Peer-to-Peer (P2P) car sharing
Brief Description of the BM
P2P car sharing platforms enable vehicle owners to rent out their cars to other users when they are not in use. This model promotes the efficient utilisation of existing vehicles, reducing the need for individual car ownership.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>Turo, formerly known as RelayRides, USA: Turo allows car owners to list their vehicles for rental, while users can rent cars directly from owners. The platform has gained popularity by offering a wide variety of vehicle options and flexibility in rental durations. Turo shows that usage is heaviest in higher-density neighbourhoods with above-average unemployment and rental housing rates.</p> <p>Drivy (now Getaround): Drivy was a popular P2P car sharing platform in Europe that allowed individuals to rent out their cars to others.</p> <p>Dégage is a membership organisation offering private cost-sharing car and bike sharing in Flanders and Brussels. As of 2022, Dégage had more than 350 shared cars, 30 shared bicycles, and almost 5,000 members. The non-profit organisation does not aim for profit but for social and liveable neighbourhoods. The organisation is driven from the bottom up by volunteers and citizens.</p> <p>Cozywheels facilitates the sharing of wheelchair-accessible vehicles between those who have one and those who need one. Several users share the vehicle owned by one of them (can also be through a joint purchase and a co-ownership). The owner uses the vehicle when needed. The rest of the time, the vehicle is at the disposal of the other group members. Flat costs related to the vehicle are shared between users on a pro-rata basis according to usage.</p> <p>GetAround is an online car sharing or peer-to-peer car sharing service that connects drivers reserving cars with car owners sharing their cars in exchange for payment. As of 2019, the company was reported to have five million users and approximately 20,000 connected cars worldwide.</p>
Successes
<p>Affordability: P2P car sharing provides cost-effective options for users, as rental prices are often competitive compared to traditional car rental agencies. An analysis of member data and usage behaviour shows that each Dégage shared car resulted in a reduction of between 4 and 18 cars.</p> <p>Efficient Resource Use: By maximising the use of existing vehicles, P2P car sharing contributes to reduced environmental impact and congestion. Vehicle sharing is an easy way to make mobility more sustainable.</p> <p>Community Building: P2P car sharing fosters a sense of community and trust among users, promoting sharing and collaboration.</p> <p>Accessibility: P2P car sharing expands access to vehicles, making it easier for individuals to find suitable transportation options when they need them.</p> <p>Variety of vehicle types: P2P car sharing offers a variety of vehicle types. For instance, Cozywheels includes vehicles equipped with accessibility features, allowing persons with reduced mobility (PRMs) to choose suitable options for their needs.</p> <p>Flexible booking: Users can book vehicles on demand, adapting to their specific needs, whether it's for medical appointments, grocery shopping, or other essential activities.</p>
Obstacles or failures
<p>Lack of Cooperation: Some governments and traditional car rental companies may resist P2P car sharing, leading to regulatory challenges and competition issues.</p>

Limited Availability: P2P car sharing services may not be available in all areas, limiting access for potential users.

Acceptance Barriers: Car owners may be hesitant to participate due to concerns about vehicle damage or misuse by some renters.

Insurance coverage concerns: users may be concerned about the potential increase in insurance costs, particularly if they have a personal car insurance policy. They might not fully understand how car sharing insurance affects their overall insurance expenses.

Vehicle maintenance responsibility: users may worry about the condition of shared vehicles and their responsibility for maintenance and repairs. This issue can discourage those who want to try out car sharing or those who are unfamiliar with car maintenance.

***Note:** platforms like [Autodelen.net](https://www.autodelen.net) offer services to strengthen shared mobility and tackle some of these barriers.

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APPENDIX H: CARSHARING 7

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

TTS Italia

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Peer-to-Peer (P2P) car sharing
Brief Description of the BM
<p>P2P is a transportation model where privately owned vehicles are shared among users through a network. A third-party company typically facilitates this sharing, managing the transactions, and retaining a percentage of the revenue. This model offers more flexible pick-up and drop-off locations compared to traditional car sharing, and it reduces operating costs by leveraging privately owned vehicles. Initially, P2P car sharing targeted dense urban centres, but there is potential for its expansion to lower-density areas due to its cost-effective nature.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>Key players in the P2P car-sharing domain include GoMore in Denmark, Snappcar and Drivy (now Getaround) in Europe, and Turo in the U.S. These platforms let individual car owners rent out their vehicles, ensuring insurance and facilitating reservations. GoMore initially began as a ridesharing platform in 2005, transforming into a for-profit entity in 2011 with added features. In 2014, they introduced P2P car rentals, offering insurance and a driver validation system. While they succeeded in providing cheaper, flexible rentals than traditional companies, demand often surpassed the supply of cars from private owners.</p>
Successes
<p>Scalability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GoMore grew from an online bulletin board to a platform with over two million members internationally, 800,000 of whom are in Scandinavia. Between 2015 and 2017, the platform quadrupled its global membership base. In Denmark, the staff count grew from 15 to 31 employees during the same period. <p>Network Effects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The platform initially grew through word-of-mouth, indicating strong network effects. By 2011, the platform had 50,000 registered members, suggesting that the more people joined, the more valuable the service became for new members. <p>Efficiency Gains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GoMore identified a mismatch between the demand for rides (passengers) and the supply (drivers) and responded by introducing a P2P car rental service to increase available rides. The platform offers rapid services without paperwork and has integrated technological developments to enhance matchmaking quality and convenience. The platform successfully transitioned from a free ride-sharing website to a model where it charges a fee for every facilitated P2P transaction. <p>Political Acceptance and Support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GoMore collaborated with Copenhagen Airport to allocate dedicated parking space for ride-sharing coordination, indicating some level of political or institutional acceptance. <p>Integration with Other Transport Modes:</p>

- GoMore, by serving as both a ride-sharing platform and a P2P car rental service, integrates various transport needs of users. This includes short-term trips, longer journeys, and other diverse mobility needs.

Obstacles or failures

GoMore's journey in the shared mobility sector illustrates the many challenges inherent to this industry. The company emerged resilient amidst other platforms collapsing due to issues like insufficient funding, the inability to amass a significant user base or flawed business models. One of GoMore's primary challenges was high competition, evidenced by its struggle to outpace platforms like BlaBlaCar and Drivy in the European market. Despite being a market leader in Scandinavia and diversifying its business model, GoMore lags in the number of cars available compared to its European competitors, likely due to the presence of established platforms when GoMore ventured into P2P car rentals.

References

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APPENDIX I: CARSHARING 8

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Porto Digital
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Santos (2018) identifies three business models: 1. Company-Owned Fleet ; 2. Modern Car Club Model ; and 3. Driver Partnership Model .
Brief Description of the BM
<p>Santos (2018) presents three distinctive business models:</p> <p>1. Company-Owned Fleet: This model involves a company owning a fleet of cars and making them available for short-term rentals to customers via an online platform. This model is currently followed by Getaround.</p> <p>2. Car Club Model: Originating in Switzerland in 1987, this model has evolved to mostly encompass one-way trips. The key difference from the original car clubs is that vehicles do not have to be returned to the same location from where they were accessed.</p> <p>3. Driver Partnership Model ("Uber-Like"): In this model, the company does not own cars but partners with ordinary car owners who act as drivers. The service is primarily operated via a company-provided app, which also handles payment processing. The company takes a percentage cut from the total income. Uber and Lyft are prime examples of this model. A point of difference is that these companies have much less stringent entry requirements for drivers compared to traditional taxi services.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>The paper doesn't provide specific details about where each business model has been deployed. However, it does mention some countries and companies associated with these models:</p> <p>1. Company-Owned Fleet: This model is used by Getaround, a company based in San Francisco, United States.</p> <p>2. Car Club Model: This model began in Switzerland in 1987 and then spread to Germany, Austria, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Denmark, Italy, Sweden, Canada, and the United States.</p> <p>3. Driver Partnership Model (Uber-like): Examples of this model include Uber and Lyft, which are popular worldwide, although the paper does not specify any particular country.</p> <p>4. New public transport on demand: Examples of this model include Blablacar and UberPool.</p>
Successes
<p>The text provided does not detail the successes pertaining to network effects, scalability, efficiency gains, environmental advantages, political acceptance, and support, or integration with other transport modes, particularly in relation to the business models. However, some implied advantages can be inferred.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Company-Owned Fleet model and the Car Club Model, with their emphasis on shared mobility, could lead to environmental advantages such as reduced carbon emissions due to fewer cars on the road. • The Driver Partnership Model ("Uber-like") has shown considerable scalability, enhancing its network effects. With an increasing number of drivers and users, the service gets more efficient and more readily available, attracting even more users. • Uber and Lyft-type models have also had their share of political challenges but have generally seen heightened acceptance as they have worked toward satisfying regulations and safety norms in multiple jurisdictions.

- Integration with other transport modes would especially be beneficial in the Car Club Model and the Company-Owned Fleet model, which could offer a complementary service for public transportation. Here too, the actual paper does not provide specifics. For comprehensive details on these aspects, further information is needed.

Obstacles or failures

Lack of alignment between business and societal goals: Companies may prioritise profit over societal benefits such as reducing traffic or emissions.

Limited space in urban areas: This can create challenges in implementing large-scale mobility services, especially in densely populated areas.

Issues to coordinate different stakeholders: Difficulty in aligning interests between company owners, drivers, users, and regulators could lead to conflicts.

Lack of communication between public authorities and mobility service providers: This can lead to legal disputes or service disruption.

Lack of acceptance or understanding by certain groups of users: Not all sections of society may be comfortable or familiar with the app-based services, limiting the user base.

Low affordability for the users: The cost of these services could be a barrier for some users, limiting overall adoption.

Technological challenges: Implementation of these models relies heavily on technology, which may present challenges in terms of infrastructure, security, privacy, etc.

Inability to attract venture capital: new entrants in this space may struggle to secure necessary funding if they can't prove a profitable business model.

High competition: The marketplace for shared mobility is competitive, which may lead to price wars and decreased profitability.

Unexpected changes in legal environment: Changes in regulations can greatly affect operation and profitability, as has been seen in some countries where ride-hailing services have faced bans or restrictions.

References

Links associated with the models presented:

Model 1 examples:

- Turo (<https://turo.com/>)
- easyCar Club (<https://carclub.easycar.com/>)
- hiyacar (<https://www.hiyacar.co.uk/>)
- Getaround (<https://www.getaround.com/>)

Model 2 examples:

- Car2Go (<https://www.car2go.com>)
- Zipcar (<https://www.zipcar.co.uk/>)
- Autolib (was based in Paris, with only electric cars available for short-term rental, but collapsed when it ran into debt and the local government refused to compensate the company for any losses)

Model 3 examples:

- Uber (<https://www.uber.com/en-GB/>)
- Lyft (<https://www.lyft.com/>)
- Sidecar (was based in San Francisco, but collapsed because it could not compete with Lyft and Uber)

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APPENDIX J: CARSHARING 9

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

Capital Region of Denmark

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
B2C car sharing
Brief Description of the BM
<p>Analysis of different shared cars and effects in Copenhagen – from companies like ShareNow, Kinto, Green Mobility, Go-more and LetsGo. (In Danish: <i>Analyse af forskellige typer delebilisme og deres effekter i København</i>)</p> <p>In 2020, there were approx. 4,410 shared cars in Copenhagen. Of these, 250 shared cars are fixed station-based, 980 are shared cars without permanent designated parking spaces and 3,180 are neighbor-to-neighbor cars. In comparison, there are 132,200 private cars in Copenhagen.</p> <p>23% of all shared cars are electric cars. In 2019, there were at least 55,000 users of carpooling to/from Copenhagen where some use Ta’med and NaboGo.</p> <p>56% of Copenhagen car-sharing users use more than one type of car-sharing scheme.</p> <p>All car-sharing schemes contribute to a greater or lesser extent to Copenhageners postponing or not buying a car.</p> <p>Less than 1% of all parking spaces on public land in Copenhagen Municipality are reserved for shared cars (only spaces are reserved today for shared cars with a fixed parking space, which is a total of 260 parking spaces).</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>This analysis concludes that all car sharing schemes have a bearing on the number of trips in one's own car. In the online survey in this study, 38% of users of both car sharing and without a fixed parking space, responded that the scheme has meant fewer trips in their own car. This share is 17% for neighbour-to-neighbour car sharing and 21% for carpooling.</p> <p>However, the analysis cannot document that it is being driven neither more nor fewer km by car due to the car-sharing schemes. Methodological difficulties make it difficult to measure in practice, whether it is the car-sharing schemes that are the cause for a possible reduced driving.</p> <p>As a starting point, it must be expected that users of car-sharing vehicles with a fixed parking space travel fewer kilometres by car than people with their own car, because it is cheaper to own a car if there is a significant driving need.</p> <p>This survey confirms that those who are members of a car-sharing scheme have a very limited need for a car, but it cannot be concluded that the car-sharing scheme is the cause of a decrease in the number of trips or kilometres driven.</p> <p>The online survey shows, for all schemes, that there is a preponderance of respondents who say they drive slightly more car trips after they have started using car sharing. But since we don't know the length of the trips, it does not necessarily mean that shared car schemes collectively lead to more driving by car, as the reductions in car journeys in absolute terms can be greater than the increases.</p>
Successes
<p>Technological developments in recent years have enabled new and smart ways to share a car. This applies both to citizens who share their cars and to companies or organisations that offer various car-sharing schemes. Moreover, several platforms have been established for carpooling that make it easier to share a trip by car. These different types of car sharing all contribute to a greater or lesser extent to Copenhageners refraining from or postponing buying a car.</p> <p>Shared cars and carpooling are additional mobility offers, that can complement public transport, cycling, walking, and private cars. Shared cars have some of the advantages of private cars, without the</p>

users having to invest in their own cars. Previous studies of shared cars with fixed parking spaces show that one shared car can replace 5-10 private cars and that these shared drivers generally drive less than private drivers. Shared cars have therefore until now been associated with being a climate-friendly alternative to the private car.

Obstacles or failures

Despite these studies, it is clear to advisers and the Municipality of Copenhagen, that there is a need for more knowledge and larger studies on this area, especially how the schemes affect young people's mobility habits. Also, there is a need to uncover their full effects on CO₂ emissions and congestion, as well as the potential urban and user benefits, such as shared cars and carpooling will be able to impart.

The lessons learned from the studies in this analysis are that users use different types of car-sharing schemes according to their needs and trip purposes, so it is important that schemes work together. The catalogue of measures shows the possibilities for initiatives that can promote car-sharing in general. For the user, it's about the entire journey; from the route to the car-sharing car, the connection between urban spaces, hubs and physical and digital infrastructure, the time spent in the car-sharing car and finally parking. These initiatives can support the entire car-sharing trip and also help highlight the added value that less parking in urban spaces can bring to citizens.

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- <https://urbancreators.dk/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/2021-Analyse-af-forskellige-typer-delebilisme-og-deres-effekter-i-Koebenhavn-Urban-Creators.pdf>

APPENDIX K: CARSHARING 10

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Arriva Denmark – SHARE NOW
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Platform-driven models (Business-to-Business B2B, Business-to-consumer B2C)
Brief Description of the BM
400 free-floating vehicles deployed in Copenhagen under the Drive Now brand (today SHARE NOW). Used as a platform-driven model for B2B and B2C trips allowing users to book and drive a car when needed. The concept is free-flowing, allowing users to drop the car off at a different location than where they picked it up. The price is per minute, hour or day. This includes all costs (parking, insurance, kilometres, charging/fuel).
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>Free-floating car sharing (FFCS) offers greater flexibility than station-based car sharing but seems to affect car ownership less. The study conducted by Haustein (2021) looks into the characteristics of people who changed or did not change car ownership over time and how an increase or decrease relates to FFCS membership, demographic, and attitudinal factors. The study is based on FFCS users (n=776) and non-users (n=720) in Copenhagen surveyed two times within 2.5 years. Five population segments were created: car dependents, car avoiders, and car limiters who showed constant but different levels of car ownership; car aspirers who increased, and car sellers who decreased car ownership over time. The segment's profiles range from car dependents who show high affective car motives, high mobility necessities, and car dependency at the one end, and car avoiders who seem more driven by environmental norms and an instrumental relation to the car, at the other end of the scale.</p> <p>A multinomial regression predicting whether car owners increased or decreased the number of cars in the household during the project period found a positive effect of FFCS membership for decreasing car ownership. However, the effect was no longer significant when adding the intention to reduce car ownership at the time of the first survey. The main factors that remained significant for changed car ownership included a change in household composition, access to a private parking space, and the initial number of cars in the household. The paper discusses policies to increase the contribution of FFCS to car ownership reduction.</p>
Successes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study found a significant effect of joining FFCS on car ownership reduction. • The availability of free-floating car services plays a role when users are considering their car ownership. • Users of free-floating services use multi-modality transportation more often than the general population with a driver's license. • Users of free-floating services are more likely to purchase an EV than non-users
Obstacles or failures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The effect disappeared when controlling for the intention to reduce car ownership.
References
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Haustein, S. (2021). What role does free-floating car sharing play for changes in car ownership? Evidence from longitudinal survey data and population segments in Copenhagen. <i>Travel Behaviour and Society</i>, 24, 181-194. https://backend.orbit.dtu.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/245028750/Haustein_car_sharing_final_accepted.pdf • https://www.europeanfinancialreview.com/car-sharing-before-and-after-the-pandemic/

APPENDIX L: CARSHARING 11

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Arriva Denmark – SHARE NOW
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Platform-driven models (B2B, B2C)
Brief Description of the BM
Free-floating car sharing users in 11 European cities
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>During the last decade, the use of free-floating car sharing systems has grown rapidly in urban areas. However, little is known about the effects free-floating car sharing offerings have on car ownership in general. Also, the main drivers of why free-floating users sell their cars are still rarely analysed.</p> <p>To shed some light on these issues, an online survey was carried out among free-floating car sharing users in 11 European cities and based the analysis on a sample of more than 10,000 survey participants. The results show that one car sharing car replaces several private cars – in optimistic scenarios up to 20 cars. In Copenhagen (followed by Rome, Hamburg, and London) one car sharing car replaces about two times more private cars than in Madrid, the city with the lowest number. The main non-city-specific influencing factor of shedding a private car due to the availability of free-floating car sharing services seems to be the usage frequency of the service. The more kilometres users drive with these cars, the more likely it becomes that they sell a private car (or they sell their car and, therefore, use this service more often). Further memberships of bike sharing and other car sharing services, users that live in larger buildings as well as users that own several cars are more likely to reduce their number of cars, too. Finally, the findings are highly valuable for car sharing operators and (transport) policymakers when introducing free-floating car sharing systems in further cities. According to our results, all 11 cities show a reduced private car fleet due to members' access to free-floating car sharing.</p>
Successes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free-floating services have a measurable effect on congestion. • In Copenhagen, 28.6% of SHARE NOW users who did not own a car indicated that they postponed buying a car. • 4.9% of users with a car indicated that they sold their car.
Obstacles or failures
References
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APPENDIX M: CARSHARING 12

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Arriva Denmark – SHARE NOW
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Platform-driven models (B2B, B2C)
Brief Description of the BM
Free-floating car sharing in Vienna
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>In cooperation with the free-floating car sharing provider SHARE NOW, an explorative study was conducted in Vienna using a digital questionnaire to collect information on motivations, usage patterns, and user characteristics.</p> <p>Almost 2,000 Viennese SHARE NOW users took part in the survey in autumn 2021. According to their statements, they were divided into four types of users: heavy users, regular users, occasional users, and non-users.</p> <p>Monetary incentives in particular are crucial for more regular use. For instance, employers can contribute to this and promote the switch to shared mobility in the form of benefits. The city administration can also provide incentives through systematic parking space management (free parking for car sharing users versus increased parking costs for one's own vehicle).</p> <p>So far, it is predominantly well-educated young men who use car sharing. The survey shows that new, additional target groups must be won over in order to get car sharing into the masses. Consequently, barriers, for example for women, need to be identified and removed.</p> <p>The study confirms that easily comprehensible and uncomplicated use, the absence of additional costs (fuel costs and insurance costs already included), as well as a free-floating system are decisive criteria for the willingness to use car sharing services.</p>
Successes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 44% of SHARE NOW users do not own a car in their household. • 21% of SHARE NOW users have reduced the number of cars in their household in the last 5 years, 50 % of them due to the high cost of private cars. • 71% of respondents would use car sharing more often or switch completely to car-sharing if it were offered as a benefit by their company. • 72% of respondents would use car sharing more often or switch completely to car-sharing if parking in the city became more expensive, but parking remained free for car-sharing users.
Obstacles or failures
References
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APPENDIX N: CROWDSIPPING

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

Porto Digital

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)

Crowdsourcing model for parcel delivery

Mourad et al. (2019) do not specifically detail a business model for shared mobility systems. However, they discuss various aspects that are important in developing such systems, including the use of models and algorithms for planning and operation. The paper identifies several areas where continued research is needed, such as trip synchronisation, traveller cost aspects, quality of service aspects, and the integration of passenger and freight transport. The paper also identifies autonomous mobility services as a significant current trend that requires further research, particularly regarding the operation and impacts of these services. Moreover, the development of models considering different objectives, like environmental issues and different sources of uncertainty, is stressed. The paper suggests the need for new public policies around these areas.

Brief Description of the BM

The paper details a **decentralised, single-tiered crowdsourcing model for parcel delivery**. Here, self-employed drivers use their excess capacity to deliver parcels while on their usual routes to work or home. The drivers provide information including their starting and ending locations, vehicle capacity, and available time windows. Similarly, customers requesting parcel delivery specify when their parcels need to be picked up and delivered. The model matches delivery requests with the driver's availability and route. When a delivery request or a new driver comes into the system, an event-based rolling horizon framework dynamically assigns tasks. Backup vehicles are used to handle deliveries that cannot be covered by ad-hoc drivers. The main goal of this model is to leverage existing, unused capacity for parcel deliveries to reduce last-mile delivery costs and overall system-wide vehicle mileage. The model achieves this by using heuristic recursive algorithms to create efficient routes.

Case studies where the BM has been implemented

The paper refers to a few case studies discussing the implementation of integrated passenger and freight transportation models:

1. Fatnassi et al. (2015) utilised a case study on the town of Corby in the UK. The integrated system reportedly provided benefits, including reduced service time and energy consumption along with lower noise and carbon emissions compared to traditional transportation systems.
2. Ghilas et al. (2016c) suggested that these systems could result in up to 16% savings on overall operational costs, indicating financial success.
3. Li et al. (2016a) considered real taxi trips in the San Francisco area and reported that mixed-taxi services can outperform other local urban area transportation systems. However, the study highlighted two key factors to maximise gains: analysis of spatial characteristics of requests and the availability of a traditional freight service.
4. Gonzalez-Feliu and Mercier (2013) studied the potential deployment of a combined people-freight approach in the city of Lyon (France). They found that an accessibility analysis showcasing the attractiveness of different urban zones is crucial before implementing this combined system.
5. Wang et al. (2016) evaluated a crowd-tasking model in Singapore using datasets from bus and taxi services. They found that crowdsourcing can handle real-time deliveries in large-scale problems and be profitable to logistic companies.

The paper did not report any explicit failures, but the studies underscored the complexity of the systems and the need for careful planning and analysis before implementation.

Successes
<p>The paper discusses the potential benefits of integrating passenger and freight transportation systems based on various case studies, yet does not detail specific instances of political acceptance, support, or integration with other transport modes. Among the noted successes:</p> <p>Efficiency Gains: Integrated systems can bring up to 16% savings on overall operational costs.</p> <p>Environmental Advantages: Such combined systems can result in reduced energy consumption, noise, and carbon emissions.</p> <p>Scalability: Case studies like the crowd-tasking model used in Singapore show these systems can work well for large-scale problems with real-time deliveries.</p> <p>Spatial Characteristics: The study emphasises the importance of analysing the spatial characteristics of requests before implementing such services, as illustrated in the San Francisco area taxi case.</p> <p>Service Time: Implementing a combined system can improve service time, as demonstrated in the Corby, UK study.</p> <p>Accessibility Analysis: The study suggests considering the accessibility of different urban zones before deploying a combined system, as shown in the city of Lyon, France.</p>
Obstacles or failures
<p>The paper does not specifically outline the obstacles or failures associated with the models discussed. However, given the nature of these delivery systems, one could presume some potential challenges that might occur:</p> <p>Alignment Between Business and Societal Goals: While these models aim to increase efficiency and reduce environmental impact, achieving a balance between profitability and societal goals can be challenging.</p> <p>Limited Space in Urban Areas: High-density urban areas may pose logistical challenges for the implementation and operation of these models.</p> <p>Coordinating Stakeholders: The system requires coordinating multiple parties including service providers, consumers, and authorities. Differences in agenda, miscommunication, or resistance to change can create obstacles.</p> <p>Technological Challenges: Dependence on advanced technologies for model operation can pose challenges, especially in areas with limited tech infrastructure.</p> <p>Legal Environment: Regulations for drones, autonomous vehicles, and data privacy may affect the feasibility of some solutions. User Acceptance: Depending on the technology used (like drones or autonomous vehicles), there might be pushback from certain groups of users due to safety concerns or lack of understanding.</p> <p>Competitive Landscape: The space is highly competitive, with multiple companies offering similar solutions. Thus, achieving a competitive edge can be a challenge.</p>
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APPENDIX O: DRT 1

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	TTS Italia
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Demand Responsive Transit (DRT) model.
Brief Description of the BM
DRT refers to a transportation system that provides flexible services based on the actual demand rather than following a fixed route or timetable. Instead of operating on regular schedules like traditional buses or trains, DRT systems adjust their routes and schedules dynamically in response to user requests. This can be particularly beneficial in areas with low population densities or during off-peak hours, where it may not be cost-effective to run regular transit services. DRT often leverages technology to manage ride requests and optimise routes in real time.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
The Tampere DRT system, PALI , part of the Nysse-Tampere transport network, offers on-demand public transport primarily for Tampere residents. PALI stands out for its flexibility, allowing advanced to spontaneous bookings, and offers free rides to the disabled and their assistants, using accessible low-floor minibuses. It is cost-effective, and special rates for seniors enhance its appeal. A significant achievement is its replication in eight Nysse municipalities. However, PALI's restricted weekday hours, a confusing booking system, and a slow post-pandemic recovery are notable challenges.
Successes
<p>Scalability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Spread: There are eight DRT systems within the Nysse region, with one in each of the municipalities. This shows that the model can be replicated and scaled across different locations, highlighting its scalability. • Diversity in Public Transport Modes: Besides the DRT, the broader Nysse public transport system includes 72 bus routes, 2 tramlines, 3 commuter train lines, and a city bike system, which indicates a robust and scalable multi-modal public transport network. <p>Network Effects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusivity: The system offers free transportation for passengers using a wheelchair, their assistants, and assistants of passengers with disabilities. Such measures encourage more users to adopt the service, enhancing the system's network effects. <p>Efficiency Gains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible Routing: Although most DRT service areas have one or two fixed stops, they use variable routes, optimising the journey based on real-time demand. <p>Environmental Advantages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focused Service Hours: The service operates from 8.30 a.m. to 2.30 p.m., which might help in reducing congestion during peak hours. • Minibuses over Large Buses: Using minibuses (14-16 seats) instead of larger buses might lead to fuel savings and reduced carbon emissions if the buses aren't typically full. <p>Political Acceptance and Support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Ownership: PALI is organised by Tuomi Logistiikka, owned by the Tampere region municipalities. • Pricing: The cost of the ride matches that of fixed public transport tickets. <p>Integration with Other Transport Modes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniform Pricing: The fact that DRT pricing is the same as other modes of public transportation (like buses) makes it easier for users to integrate and switch between different modes.

- **Service Overlap:** The DRT system complements the existing extensive public transport system, including bus routes, tramlines, commuter train lines, and a city bike system, providing a seamless experience for commuters.

Obstacles or failures

In the City of Tampere's DRT system, several challenges are evident. The service operates only from 8.30 a.m. to 2.30 p.m. on weekdays, potentially excluding users with obligations outside these hours. The booking method is bifurcated between calling a general number for some areas and directly contacting the driver for others, leading to possible user confusion. The pandemic led to a 26% reduction in trips in 2020, and even before COVID-19, the system's reach was limited, accounting for just 0.6% of total Nysse region trips in 2019. Each minibus, with its 14–16 seat capacity, may struggle to meet demand peaks, potentially sidelining non-pre-booked users. With 19% of Tampere's population over 64, the challenge remains to diversify the appeal across all age groups, especially when the booking relies heavily on traditional calling methods in an increasingly digital age.

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APPENDIX P: DRT 2

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Porto Digital
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
<p>DRT system</p> <p>The paper does not present a business model. It focuses on demonstrating an application of an intermediate modelling framework for introducing a Demand Responsive Transport (DRT) system in Thessaloniki, Greece. The primary aim of this system is to enhance resource efficiency in regions with low population density through the implementation of flexible bus routes. The study does not delve into the business aspects such as revenue generation, cost structure, or value proposition. The main focal point is to use the modelling framework to evaluate the possible implementation and potential impact of such a transport system.</p>
Brief Description of the BM
<p>The paper does not provide specific details about the intermediate modelling framework used for the introduction of a DRT system. However, it discusses the application of the framework in a case study for Thessaloniki, Greece. In this case study, the framework is used to provide an analysis of introducing a DRT service in an area with low population density. The DRT service involves the use of a small fleet (4 vehicles) of minibuses with large capacity (50 seats each) to serve the demand of 164 trips during the peak hour. The framework considers key performance indicators (KPIs) like the number of trips served by one DRT vehicle, average travel distance, average service time, in-vehicle time, and waiting time. While the specific methodology or workflow of the intermediate modelling framework is not clearly stated, it is implied that it involves the evaluation of KPIs and analysis of different scenarios to assess the feasibility and impact of introducing a DRT service. The model serves to simulate and evaluate the system without needing to implement it physically, thus offering insights into its potential performance and viability.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>Based on the information provided in the paper, the intermediate modelling framework developed in the EU H2020 project MOMENTUM has been implemented in four cities: Madrid, Leuven, Regensburg, and Thessaloniki. However, the paper does not offer specific case studies or significant details regarding the successes or failures of each implementation. It only states that the framework has been validated and used successfully in previous studies (Vanherck et al., Salanova et al., Narayanan et al., and Martín et al.), especially for providing quantitative results on the impacts of a growing shared mobility ecosystem, even with limited additional data.</p>
Successes
<p>The paper does not provide detailed information about the specific successes of the intermediate modelling framework. However, based on the case study of Thessaloniki, and the general nature of DRT systems, several potential successes can be inferred:</p> <p>Scalability: The paper mentions examining small fleet sizes for the DRT system. This suggests that the framework can accommodate varying demand levels, allowing the service to expand or reduce fleet size depending on needs.</p> <p>Efficiency Gains: DRT systems aim to provide efficient use of transport resources particularly in areas of low population density. The modelling framework aids in achieving and evaluating this objective.</p> <p>Environmental Advantages: DRT systems reduce the need for heavily trafficked fixed route systems, potentially decreasing vehicle emissions, although the paper does not mention concrete findings.</p> <p>Integration with other transport modes: The model development process likely included an assessment of how the DRT system could integrate with existing transport infrastructure and services.</p> <p>Political acceptance and support: While not explicitly mentioned in the segment provided, implementing a DRT system is often heavily reliant on local government support. By demonstrating</p>

potential benefits through the framework, authorities might be more inclined to back the implementation of a DRT system.

The study did not mention network effects specifically, and the effectiveness or success of the system in terms of the aforementioned aspects would likely be dependent on specific local factors in each use case.

Obstacles or failures

The paper does not provide detailed specifics about the failures or obstacles experienced during the implementation of the intermediate modelling framework developed under the EU H2020 project MOMENTUM. The primary focus in the given context is the successful implementation and validation of the framework across various cities and studies.

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APPENDIX Q: MAAC

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

TM

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Mobility as a Common (MaaC)
Brief Description of the BM
MaaC is shared mobility owned, maintained, and serviced by local citizens for local citizens.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
The Hague and Amsterdam. There are two in Amsterdam and seven in The Hague.
Successes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This business model matches demand and supply, it only provides what is needed. That also means that the societal value is aligned with the business value. If it doesn't create any societal value, then for the citizens it is not a good plan. • People take responsibility for the assets and their own behaviour because they face the consequences of it. The assets cannot be treated poorly anonymously, because people know the cooperative partners. Thus, users have a broader sense of responsibility for the assets and also for the public space.
Obstacles or failures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of the difficult things is how to get started. These initiatives have an implementation cost that needs to be subsidised or paid for by someone. In a classical business model, there is an investor who gets his/her money back afterwards. However, for many reasons, an investor is not desired. Being independent of capital-extracting forces brought forward by the start-up mentality is paramount for MaaC to remain ethically coherent. In the end, the citizens always pay the price. We strongly believe transparency of what this price is, is paramount to maintain the integrity of the community. Lack of budget is also one of the reasons why it is so difficult to scale up these initiatives. If there was a budget, they could start in 100 places at the same time and move forward more quickly. • Another difficult thing is how to train people to do what Townmaking (TM) does because currently we are the only ones doing it. Our specific vision of society and how to develop societal assets requires a profound understanding of an array of forces present in our society. It also requires a specific ethical stance on our world today. A Townmaker is vulnerable because of this. Not everyone is willing or able to handle this vulnerability. The tenacity needed to create a successful sharing community needs to be embodied by the person building these communities. This fact also adversely affects the scalability of the business model, since we are limited by the staff we have. We are addressing this challenge through a project with the Ministry in the Netherlands, but we have to train the people who then help to implement these initiatives in other cities. We believe we can find the people and give them a purposeful role in society. The Ministry shares this belief and in the coming 5 years we will focus on building local teams of Townmakers to scale MaaC in the Netherlands. • Currently, only round trips are allowed. However, this drawback might be solved once MaaC is sufficiently escalated and assets could be shared across neighbourhoods or even between cities (e.g. free-floating vehicles).
References
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For now, we only know of our initiatives. They can all be found on the website of DEEL: http://wijzijndeel.nl

APPENDIX R: MAAS 1

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

5T Srl

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Bundle of mobility services with a monthly subscription
Brief Description of the BM
<p>By paying a monthly subscription plan, the user has access to several means of transportation. Each way of transportation is available up to a maximum ceiling selected in advance either by choice of the user or by offer of the MaaS Operator (e.g. minutes for sharing mobility, km for taxis).</p> <p>This business model does not just cover individual travel movements, it also meets the full daily mobility needs of individuals and families by offering different means of transport.</p> <p>There are two main variables for the MaaS Operator to make margins: the supplying of mobility services and the % of usage by the customer.</p> <p><u>Variable of margin n° 1: the MaaS Operator buys in advance at a discount.</u></p> <p>The MaaS Operator can purchase mobility service minutes in bulk from integrated Mobility Service Providers (MSPs). This action can give a certain amount of discount to the MaaS Operator.</p> <p>Let's see an example.</p> <p>User A pays 150€ per month. In their plan, User A has public transportation (worth 40€), 70€ as a taxi voucher, and 200 minutes for bike sharing (worth 60€). User A perceives the value of the offer: by paying 150€ in advance, User A has the possibility of using 170€ of mobility services. Let's imagine that the MaaS Operator bought each service at 20% off from price on the market (if it is sustainable for the MSPs). It means that it bought the public transportation monthly ticket at 32€, the taxi voucher at 56€, and the minutes for bike sharing at 48€. That would be a total cost of 136€. By this, for each user, the MaaS Operator would be gaining 14€.</p> <p>The MaaS Operator's ability to buy mobility services in bulk and at discounted rates creates a win-win situation. While users enjoy the convenience of bundled services at a competitive price, MSPs benefit from a guaranteed volume of business.</p> <p><u>Variable of margin n° 2: the user does not fulfil all of the services that they bought.</u></p> <p>Let's imagine that in a specific month, User A uses 20€ of taxi and 30 minutes of bike sharing, the MaaS Operator still has a "stock" of 50€ of taxi and 170 minutes of bike sharing.</p> <p>The MaaS Operator will postpone the purchase (and the cost) of new minutes, but it will not postpone the upfront income from the user.</p> <p><u>Dimensions, benefits, and implications</u></p> <p>This type of business model works better in urban areas, where there is a high availability of mobility services, and the MaaS Operator "just" integrates and combines them.</p> <p>It can help users reduce car use and families avoid having to buy an extra car to get around cities.</p> <p>These results have been recorded by some pilots and projects. We will dive a little deeper into it in the success part of this template.</p> <p>The biggest implications are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • smooth technical integration between MSPs and MaaS Operator • giving the customer a better user experience through the MaaS Operator rather than the single MSP • providing excellent customer service by the MaaS Operator to the user • the more tailor-made is the bundles for the user, the better
Case studies where the BM has been implemented

Mobility vouchers (Turin, Italy)³

"Mobility Vouchers" was a MaaS project launched by the City of Turin (Italy) in collaboration with 5T Srl. The project involved the allocation of mobility vouchers worth 150€ per month to 100 citizens selected through a public call for applications.

The vouchers could be used to access various mobility services, including public transport, car sharing, and scooter sharing.

None of the selected testers owned a car during the project. It was a mandatory requirement. So, this initiative tested for one year what would happen if we substituted private cars with MaaS mobility packages.

Whim (Helsinki, Finland)⁴

Whim is a MaaS platform that has been implemented in several cities, including Helsinki, Vienna, and Birmingham. The platform offers users a monthly subscription plan that provides access to various modes of transportation, such as public transportation, car sharing, and bike sharing.

Some plans give you access to a monthly ticket for public transportation, plus a set of minutes of sharing mobility, plus a discount on taxi/ride-hailing.

UbiGo (Gothenburg, Sweden)^{5 6}

This Swedish pilot project ran from 2013 to 2014. It was one of the world's first MaaS projects, with very little technology implementation. It enabled families living in Gothenburg to buy prepaid bundles geared to their individual mobility requirements, and it produced very interesting results (such as a drop in private car usage and lower traffic).

Successes

All the mentioned case studies created interesting results and knowledge.

The "Mobility voucher" project tested also different types of bundles, to test the reaction and the behaviours of the users.

Here are explained 3 main successes: (i) the role of public transportation in a MaaS offer, (ii) the impact of high customisation for the end user, and (iii) the environmental benefits.

Whim and UbiGo generated good knowledge regarding simplicity and user experience, and private car usage.

Public transportation

In the "Mobility Vouchers" project, the least used package has been the one without public transportation. This suggests that public transportation plays a pivotal role in the MaaS ecosystem. The answer to "Is public transportation the backbone of MaaS?" seems to be "yes".

High customisation

The most used packages (still in the "Mobility Vouchers" project) have been the ones with a high focus on user habits: not being willing to drive (23%) and being safe from outer weather (37%).

Environmental successes

Additionally, 5T analysed the project's environmental benefits: by travelling with alternatives to private cars, users emitted a 50% lower amount of CO₂ than travelling with their own vehicle.

Simplicity and User Experience

This business model can positively influence people to use alternatives to private vehicles: by offering an up-front payment structure, like the ones seen in systems such as UbiGo and Whim, instead of a pay-as-you-go approach, the process becomes simpler.

People only need to "unlock" their travel using a ticket or app, that they already purchased and paid.⁷

³ <https://www.muoversiatorino.it/en/maastorino-en/>

⁴ <https://whimapp.com/helsinki/en/plans/>

⁵ <https://maas-alliance.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/MaaS-brochure-ENG.pdf>

⁶ https://whimapp.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/MaaSGlobal_History.pdf

⁷ <https://nationalcenterformobilitymanagement.org/blog/mobility-as-a-service-further-integration/>

Car usage

With UbiGo in Sweden, car use has significantly dropped: 44% of the participants decreased their use of private cars. Furthermore, UbiGo has had a positive effect on the perception of alternatives to privately owned cars.

Obstacles or failures⁸

User Adoption

Users might hesitate to commit to a fixed monthly fee for accessing a set of services or products, preferring a pay-as-you-go approach where they only pay for what they use. This hesitation depends on users' awareness of their typical transportation habits, modes, and costs, which is generally not high (yet).

Coordination and Integration between MaaS Operator and MSPs

In this business model, the MaaS Operator must oversee every aspect of the user's journey. This includes real-time vehicle availability on the map, vehicle unlocking, providing information like fuel or battery levels, handling payments and clearing, customer care, and delivering a superior user experience compared to individual MSPs. Achieving this requires a high level of automation and technical integration.

Furthermore, usually, there is another stakeholder in between, the MaaS Integrator.

Splitting the roles, the MaaS Integrator has the technical one, and the MaaS Operator, the commercial one.

Income levels

Profitability is a broader challenge within the MaaS sector.

The initial step involves setting up a system where all stakeholders earn margins with each user or journey.

Next, it's crucial to attract enough active customers and manage a significant volume of journeys to sustain the business.

Simply investing in marketing to promote one MaaS Operator over another one isn't enough. Not all target users are fully attuned to or aware of the advantages of MaaS, making awareness and behavioural alignment important factors.

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APPENDIX S: MAAS 2

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	5T Srl
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
MSP-Driven MaaS Integration / Mobility Super App
Brief Description of the BM
<p>In this business model, a Mobility Service Provider (MSP) expands its offerings by becoming a Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) Operator. The MSP enhances its existing app by integrating various transportation services such as public transportation, taxis, car rentals, shared bikes, and scooters. This transformation allows users to access and pay for multiple modes of transportation within a single app, receiving a comprehensive mobility solution. It also allows the MSP to keep the users within its application and its customer journey and experience.</p> <p>Companies that embrace this business model present themselves as “super app for mobility”.</p> <p>Regarding revenues and finances, the integrated MSP acknowledges a commission (usually between 5% and 10%) to the MaaS Operator.</p> <p>This business model can have a sub-category where the MSP that becomes the MaaS Operator is the Local Public Transport Operator. Another similar business model is where a brand or a product from another industry integrates a mobility service (e.g., the possibility to pay the parking toll via mobile banking, or to buy bus tickets via the car insurance app).</p> <p>In this template, we will focus on the “general category”. The main successes and obstacles can however relate to all of these sub-business models.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>Recently, several MSPs started to deploy the “super app” for mobility.</p> <p>FreeNow</p> <p>FreeNow is the “Mobility Super App” with a wide transportation choice for consumers across Europe available in 9 markets and in over 150 cities. Users can access several types of mobility services within a single app including taxis, Ride (PHV), Car sharing, eScooters, eBikes and eMopeds, and public transport. FREE NOW aggregates numerous mobility brands with the ambition to make urban mobility more efficient and sustainable without adding new vehicles on the street.</p> <p>It was founded in 2009, as an app for booking taxis. In 2019, thanks to the joint venture between car makers BMW and Daimler, several companies and services have been created:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reach now: for offering multimodal mobility services (public transport, car sharing, bike sharing, and ride-hailing); • Charge now: an app for charging points for electric vehicles; • Park now: an app for reserving and paying for parking; • Free now: for taxi and ride-hailing; • Share now: for free-floating car sharing (merge between Car2go and DriveNow). <p>In 2022, the Free Now app becomes “the mobility super app”, integrating almost all of the services of the group: public transportation, sharing mobility (car, scooter, bike, moped), ride-hailing (and taxis). Thanks to this high level of integration within the same app, FreeNow can easily offer a corporate MaaS to companies interested in giving this benefit to employees. The company sets a mobility budget for the employee, and the employee finds it in their wallet within the FreeNow for Business application.</p> <p>Uber</p> <p>Uber is well known as a revolutionary app for ride-hailing. Without owning a single car or taxi and without hiring any driver, Uber reached over 10,000 cities in 70 countries. The expansion of mobility offers to users started in 2019, when Uber integrated the possibility to check and pay for public transportation within its own app. Now Uber can provide, within the same application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ride-hailing (the first service provided) and taxis, also by sharing the trip

- Car rental
- Micromobility sharing (bikes, scooters, mopeds)
- Public transportation

Uber also provides other services from other industries: food delivery, trucks, payment and reward platforms, and insurance.

Helbiz

Helbiz is a MSP for e-scooter sharing founded in 2019. In the Helbiz app, the user can access not only mobility services but also services from other industries:

- Mobility: scooter sharing (the native service of Helbiz), moped sharing (by Helbiz), and taxis (in partnership with another MSP)
- Sport and entertainment streaming: deep link that opens Helbiz Live
- Insurance (in partnership with Yolo, an insurtech)
- Audioguides for visiting the city (Helbiz City Guide)
- Food delivery (Helbiz Kitchen)

The integration with sports and entertainment streaming works both ways:

- In the monthly pre-paid plan of mobility is included access to Helbiz Live (and to Helbiz Kitchen)
- Users of Helbiz Live have a discount code for using mobility services pay-as-you-go

Successes

Positive brand influence

When established, MSPs expand their offerings to include a super app for mobility, their existing brand recognition can play a pivotal role in the success of the new offering. Users can associate the established brand with reliability and trust, which can boost adoption rates and user loyalty.

This brand influence can be a significant advantage in the competitive super app mobility space.

Minimal behavioral change

In contrast to many other MaaS business models, this approach requires minimal changes in user behaviour. Users can seamlessly access and utilise various mobility services within the single app they are already used to, reducing the need for significant alterations in their transportation habits.

Offering an integrated user experience

In this business model, the MSP can extend its offer to its own customers, increasing their retention even when they don't use the MSP's native service. For example:

- the public transport operator can suggest kick scooters for the last mile or when the next bus is expected after 30 minutes;
- ride-hailing operators (Taxis, Uber, Lyft) can suggest car sharing or buses when no drivers are available at the moment or if they are too far;
- sharing mobility operators can show right away the information about public transportation and, as an alternative, propose their services (car sharing, taxis, scooters, etc.).

In some cases, as seen with Helbiz, the integrated user experience can expand to other industries.

Scalability and network effects

One of the primary successes of this business model is its scalability. By integrating multiple transportation services within a single app, these platforms can expand rapidly to new markets and cities. For example, FreeNow, operating in over 150 cities across Europe, demonstrates the scalability of the super app concept.

These platforms also benefit from strong network effects, where more users joining the platform increases the value of the service for everyone. In Uber's case, being available in over 10,000 cities and 70 countries creates a global network that attracts both riders and drivers. The same holds for other MSPs that can be integrated, such as Lime, Voi, and Helbiz (regarding e-scooters).

Environmental and political synergy

Super apps drive eco-friendly mobility choices by integrating shared transportation services. They align with urban sustainability goals, reducing emissions and congestion, thus gaining the support of public authorities.

Efficiency gains

Integration of various mobility services into one app leads to efficiency gains. Users can plan, book, and pay for various transportation modes seamlessly, reducing the need to switch between multiple apps or payment systems. This convenience enhances the user experience and encourages more usage.

Obstacles or failures

Coordination among stakeholders

Effective coordination among multiple stakeholders, such as public transportation agencies, ride-hailing services, and bike-sharing companies, can be intricate. Ensuring smooth collaboration and data sharing among these entities can be a challenge, impacting the quality of integrated services.

High competition

The super app mobility space is highly competitive, with numerous players fighting for market share. Competition can lead to pricing wars and increased marketing expenses, impacting profitability.

Limited space in urban areas and vehicle availability

In densely populated urban areas, the availability of sufficient space for various transportation modes can pose significant challenges. Finding suitable parking, docking, or pick-up locations for different modes can be a logistical challenge. This limitation in space not only affects the integration of these services but also impacts the availability of vehicles, potentially leading to user inconvenience.

Technological integration

Seamless integration of different mobility services depends on technological compatibility and standards. Misalignment or a lack of interoperability among systems can fragment the user experience, making it challenging to transition between different modes of transportation.

Achieving technological harmony is essential for providing a smooth and effortless user experience.

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APPENDIX T: MAAS 3

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	5T Srl
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
<p>Integrated mobility platform Pay-as-you-go / Pay-per-use business model</p>
Brief Description of the BM
<p>The user has an application on their smartphone. After entering the destination, the application suggests the best ways to reach it, among the services integrated.</p> <p>The Pay-As-You-Go MaaS Model brings together different types of transportation like buses, taxis, and bikes into one app. Instead of paying a fixed fee each month, the users only pay for the rides and the consumption they use.</p> <p>Regarding revenues and finances, the integrated MSPs acknowledge a commission (usually between 5% and 10%) to the MaaS Operator for each sale or transaction.</p> <p>In this template, we will talk about those business models where the MaaS Operator does not provide any means of transportation. It just integrates the services and offers them to the user.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>BIPforMaaS Pilot (Turin and Piedmont Region, Italy)^{9 10}</p> <p>In collaboration with 5T, Piedmont Region was the first public administration in Italy to try the demand incentive model based on cashback.</p> <p>250 users had the opportunity to test MaaS in Turin through the use of a single application, with the possibility of also enjoying a monthly cashback of 50%, in the period from June to September 2022. In one single app, users had access to train tickets, e-scooters, taxis, car sharing, parking, and public transport infomobility. Users received every month a cashback of 50% of the expenses, up to 15€ per month.</p> <p>Both data and survey to users show interesting results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • demand was stimulated until it exceeded the minimum threshold necessary to obtain the cashback; • on one hand, users focused on taking their usual modes of transport; • on the other hand, occasionally, and thanks to the ease of access through a single application, users took the opportunity to try out new modes of transport. <p>The project was completely funded by Piedmont Regione to test the MaaS, the business model, the incentive to users through cashback, and the users' behaviour.</p> <p>MooneyGo (Ex MyCicero)</p> <p>MooneyGo is an app with a wide range of mobility services. Users can buy public transport single fares and passes, pay for car parking, and enjoy many other mobility services in the same app. It's also possible to top up the "MooneyGo credit" and pay cash for public transport passes booked from the app at more than 45,000 Mooney stores.¹¹</p> <p>The MSPs pay a commission to MooneyGo for every ticket, ride, or sale of their mobility service. No extra costs for the user.¹² The user pays the same price whether they buy through the MaaS Operator or the MSPs.</p>

⁹ <https://www.bipformaas.it/en/the-results-of-the-bipformaas-trial/>

¹⁰ <https://maas-alliance.eu/2022/08/09/5t-launches-its-first-maas-trial-in-the-piemonte-region-italy/>

¹¹ <https://mooneygroup.it/what-we-do/services-products/>

¹² <https://www.economyup.it/mobilita/mobility-as-a-service/digitalizzare-la-mobilita-quotidiana-la-sfida-di-mooneygo/>

On one hand, the MSP gives up the direct relationship with the customer, and also some of its revenue because of the commission. On the other hand, the MSP gives up the costs of acquiring new customers and keeping them.

As a “platform business”, a large number of active users is the added value of the MaaS Operator towards MSPs for integrating them.

Notable to say that the company is not exclusively a MaaS Operator. Mooneygo is part of Mooney Group, a financial group that focuses on proximity banking. The group acquired Pluservice and MyCicero. MyCicero became MooneyGo, for interfacing the users as MaaS Operator. Pluservice acts as MaaS Integrator, interfacing with local public administration.

Urbi¹³

Urbi presents itself as an aggregator of active shared mobility services in a city, simplifying their use for the end user. It's available in 33 cities in 11 countries. In the same application, the user has the possibility to:

- buy tickets for trains, airport shuttles, ferries;
- call a taxi or ride-hailing service;
- rent a vehicle in sharing (bike, scooter, moped, car), it can be done within the Urbi app or on the app of the MSP (with a deep link in Urbi's app);
- find and use electric charging columns within the app.

In addition, Urbi offers the opportunity to buy different package/voucher combining some of the mobility services available on the platform.

Again, the MSPs pay a commission to Urbi for every sale of their mobility service. No extra costs for the user. The user pays the same price whether they buy through the MaaS Operator or through the MSPs.

Notable to say that Urbi is controlled by Telepass for 70% (after buying it from Lastminute.com and Urbi's founders). Due to its strong shareholder, the company financing relies on debt capital instead of risk capital.

Successes

Friendly user experience

The pay-as-you-go model is designed with user convenience in mind. Its simplicity of understanding and ease of use have been major successes. Users appreciate the simplicity of paying for rides only when needed. This flexibility allows individuals to easily combine and switch between various modes of transportation, providing them with a seamless and user-friendly mobility experience.

Scalability

The integrator model has demonstrated scalability by efficiently integrating various modes of transportation, such as public transport, taxis, and shared mobility services, on a large scale, especially if the integrated MSP is an international player. This ensures that a wide range of transportation options is available to users within a single application, and an easier entrance to a new city for the MaaS Operator.

Political acceptance and support

The integrator model has gained notable political acceptance and support. Public authorities recognise it as a viable solution to address urban mobility challenges. By promoting the integrator model, they aim to reduce traffic congestion and limit pollution resulting from the excessive use of private cars. This alignment with governmental objectives has been a significant success, fostering a conducive environment for integrated mobility solutions.

Obstacles or failures

In this business model, the main obstacles (or challenges) regard the end user.

Critical customer base and constant usage

¹³ https://h2020-gecko.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/GECKO_D1.4_Final_update_of_new_mobility_services_and_business_models.pdf

The revenues for the MaaS Operator consist of a commission per sale. To be profitable, it is needed a high number of users and a high number of rides or tickets purchased through the application. Bringing customers and keeping them is a major challenge of every business model. In this case, there is a matter of customer habit.

Customer habit

Are customers used to buying directly through the specific MSPs? This can be a good obstacle to making the BM sustainable. The MSP can become both a supplier of the MaaS Operator and a competitor.

Challenging user experience

On the flip side of the user experience as a success, the lack of a proper, simple, seamless, excellent, and user-friendly experience can be a significant obstacle for this MaaS business model. When users encounter difficulties in understanding or navigating the system, it can lead to reduced usage and, in some cases, project or company failures.

The success of such a model is highly dependent on delivering a user experience that is intuitive, hassle-free, and attractive to customers. Failure to meet these expectations can pose a substantial hindrance.

Full integration of the MSP

The case studies (especially the BIPforMaaS pilot) show that full integration is the best type of customer experience.

Unfortunately, sometimes the MaaS Operator cannot fully integrate the MSP. The light integration is available (a link for opening the MSP's app) but it reduces user satisfaction.

Sometimes it can be a technical challenge, sometimes a commercial challenge, sometimes both.

Financial sustainability

All mentioned case studies are financially backed by a bigger player (Piedmont Region, Mooney, Telepass). This business model doesn't seem to be profitable on its own yet.

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APPENDIX U: MAAS 4

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Forum Virium Helsinki
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
B2C MaaS subscription model
Brief Description of the BM
Mobility-as-a-Service, by having all different transport modes from MaaS operator, even by monthly subscription
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
MaaS Global / Whim
Successes
MaaS as a concept is a Finnish innovation success that made its way even to the country's legislation five years ago. Founded by one of the MaaS concept evangelists Sampo Hietanen, MaaS Global and its Whim app have gathered big media attention and investments.
Obstacles or failures
MaaS Global / Whim has struggled even in its home area as the Helsinki Region Transport Authority (HSL) has not provided any discounts for Whim users on their public transport tickets. Having public transport through Whim cannot be offered profitably at the same price that customers get directly from HSL. The business model of monthly subscription MaaS is really price-sensitive and has not yet proven to be really working in many real-life cases. Customers would need to be willing to pay Whim a premium on top of the existing transport services.
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APPENDIX V: MAAS 5

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Forum Virium Helsinki
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
B2C on-demand door-to-door MaaS travel chain
Brief Description of the BM
Mobility-as-a-service, selling the whole journey from door to door as one ticket
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
Matkahuolto
Successes
MaaS as a concept is a Finnish innovation success that made its way even to the country's legislation five years ago. Matkahuolto, as the service and marketing company of Finnish bus transport, has made the most out of the travel chains made possible through open APIs, etc. made possible in the Act on Transport Services (see links below).
Obstacles or failures
Not all companies have opened their ticketing APIs as the legislation demands. Making easy travel chains by different transport methods would be difficult anyway – especially in Finland which has low population density and long distances, and therefore in many cases not much public transport.
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APPENDIX W: MAAS 6

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

European Passengers' Federation

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Mobility-as-a-Service platform-based business model
Brief Description of the BM
The MaaS platform-based business model integrates different transportation services into a single digital platform, offering users a seamless and convenient way to plan, book, and pay for their journeys. This model provides access to multiple modes of transportation, including public transit, ridesharing, bike sharing, e-scooters, etc. in one application.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>The Whim application (Helsinki, Finland) is a good example of a successful MaaS platform. Users can select and pay for various transportation options, making it easier to combine different modes for a complete journey. The success of the Whim app can be attributed to its user-friendly interface, comprehensive coverage, and integration with public transport. Whim is also available in Turku (Finland), Antwerp (Belgium), Vienna (Austria), and West Midlands (UK), multiple cities in Switzerland and Greater Tokyo (Japan).</p> <p>CityX platform: subscribers can seamlessly switch between different modes using a single app.</p> <p>Floya: a Brussels-based app that was launched on 6 September 2023. It combines the four public transport operators in Brussels (metro, tram, bus, and train), in addition to shared scooter, bike, and car services.</p> <p>Meep: an app that integrates all available (public and private) modes of transport. Meep operates in Lisbon, Málaga, Valencia, Malta, Sevilla, Asturias and Cyprus. It collaborates with public institutions, public transport operators, and private mobility companies.</p> <p>Hoppin: in Flanders (Belgium), Hoppin bundles different transport solutions into mobility hubs, such as trains, trams, buses, and shared mobility (e.g., bicycles, cars, and scooters). Hoppin points may also provide access to parcel or luggage lockers, or a bicycle repair service. Hoppin will launch a travel planner in 2024.</p>
Successes
<p>Scalability: MaaS platforms can quickly scale to accommodate a large user base making the included mobility services accessible to a wide range of users. Floya, for example, plans to expand and add new mobility services and functions as the Brussels mobility network evolves.</p> <p>Efficiency gain: Users have the flexibility to combine different modes of transport into one route, depending on their plans and needs. Users can also optimise their routes based on real-time information about disruptions and detours, thus reducing travel time, pollution, and congestion.</p> <p>Integration: MaaS platforms encourage the use of sustainable modes like public transport, cycling, and e-scooters (promoting eco-friendly mobility choices). Before the launch of MaaS solutions, people needed multiple apps if they wanted to access the full range of transport options in a city. Hoppin has specific "Hoppin points", which are mobility hubs where different means of transport are centralised so that people can easily switch from one mode of transport to another. These are also quite visible to people on the street.</p> <p>Ease of payment: Many MaaS solutions, like Floya, offer a variety of payment options, as well as ticketing options such as multi-journey passes for the bus or train. In Meep and others, users can pay for a multi-modal trip in one transaction, regardless of how many transport providers were involved in the route.</p> <p>Political acceptance: Governments often support MaaS initiatives to improve urban mobility and reduce traffic congestion. Floya, for example, was created as a collaboration between STIB-MIVB (Brussels Intercommunal Transport Company) and Brussels Mobility (Brussels Regional Public Service). Hoppin</p>

points are managed as a collaboration among road managers, local authorities, transport regions, traffic agencies, the bus operator, and other mobility managers.

Flexibility and user preferences: MaaS can be tailored to a user's preferences and needs. When planning a journey in the Meep app, users can choose routes that are for example 'greener', 'faster', or 'cheaper'. Hoppin offers "flexible transport" upon request when the train, bus, or tram are not accessible due to either the location, the time, or a mobility limitation. Additionally, because MaaS generates data related to user preferences, needs, and demands, it can improve insights and give operators, authorities, and policymakers a better understanding of these aspects. This can lead to improved service offerings.

Accessibility: accessible MaaS helps various groups of people, especially those facing mobility challenges and transportation barriers (PRM, people with disabilities and mental health conditions, the elderly, tourists, caregivers, urban planners, local authorities, etc).

Promote sustainable travel: By improving the integration of transport systems and services, advocates claim that MaaS could lead to a reduction in car use and/or car ownership. By providing easier access to personal transport services (including car hire companies, car-sharing clubs, and taxis) and by facilitating more informed decisions about which mode(s) of travel to use in a certain set of circumstances, it is possible that the need to use or own a car would be reduced.

Obstacles or failures

Lack of alignment: some MaaS platforms may find it difficult to align broader societal goals, especially if they prioritise profit over sustainability.

Lack of acceptance: The availability of transport options can vary from place to place, as does how these options are presented to the public. This can result in the creation of long-term habits for moving around, with people often relying on one mode of transport (e.g. by purchasing a car or transport subscription). In general, people must be willing to change these transport habits. It is also important to note that certain user groups, for instance, the elderly or less tech-savvy individuals, may also find MaaS apps challenging to adopt and use.

Cooperation challenges: coordination between public authorities and various providers can be difficult and hinder effective MaaS implementation.

Difficult subscription models and pricing schemes: There must be coordination between different transport providers (e.g. metro, taxi, bike-sharing providers) to offer a joint mobility subscription across modes. In the Floya app for example, some available transport providers, such as the car-sharing app Cambio, users must still have the provider's app on their phones because the two apps are linked. Additionally, in Meep's business model, Meep receives a commission per trip, though it is not clear how much this affects or increases pricing for end-users.

Ticketing integration challenges: Existing public transport services must offer the possibility to scan and validate smartphone tickets/codes for a MaaS solution or app to be fully integrated.

Data sharing challenges: real-time information requires certain technology and data formats from providers, which can be a challenge.

Strict legal frameworks: some countries have strict regulations about who can sell transport tickets.

Data privacy concerns: not all users are comfortable with sharing data like their personal information, travel habits, or preferences.

Barriers to accessibility: digital mobility solutions, like MaaS applications, are not accessible to all members of society. Certain groups (e.g. people with physical or cognitive disabilities, people with low income, migrants/ethnic minorities, older people, children, women, etc.) may not have the knowledge, skills, interest, tools, or money to access or use them.

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APPENDIX X: MAAS 7

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	TTS Italia
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
MaaS Platform
Brief Description of the BM
MaaS combines various transport services like public transit, car-sharing, ride-hailing, and bike-sharing into a unified platform. Users benefit from seamless planning, booking, and payment. The business thrives on partnerships with transport providers and tech platforms. Revenue is generated through subscriptions, pay-per-use, or advertising.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
Four case studies have been considered, in which a MaaS Platform has been implemented: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. UbiGo platform implementation in Gothenburg, Sweden. 2. Whim platform implementation In Helsinki, Finland. 3. OpenMove's MaaS platform in Trento region (North Italy). 4. ENABLE MaaS platform from Tactran consortium in Tayside and Central Scotland.
Successes
<p>The various implementations of MaaS platforms showed several aspects of success both in an increased use of public transport, which indirectly revolves into less fuel consumption and in social acceptance. A considerable aspect is the dematerialisation of tickets, through the Apps/Platforms, which means both significant savings in material and distribution costs for the municipality/region/province and, furthermore, the possibility to communicate with users in real time. Below are brief considerations of each project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UbiGo implementation provided the following statistics regarding the modal shift: 46% of the users reported greater bus/tram use, 44% less private car use, and 51% greater car sharing use; while specifically related to user acceptance, 68% of the users perceived having more alternatives from which to choose, 49% perceived a reduced transportation expenditure and 69% perceived that it became easier to pay and keep track of transportation. • Whim project achieved an increase of public transport (PT) modal share in Helsinki by 48%. Whim users combine taxis 3x more often with PT compared to the typical Helsinki resident. In addition, 12% of bike trips are taken within 30 minutes before PT trip and 30% of bike trips happen within 90 minutes after PT trip. • The success of the OpenMove platform can be observed in the 2.5 million trips made per year, 100,000 registered users and 15% of the tickets sold via OpenMove MaaS, making it the first suburban platform implemented in Europe. The project demonstrated how a scalable MaaS approach is possible thanks to a 3-level intervention: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An Account-Based ticketing system. - A MaaS Integration layer to systematise all forms of transport. - A MaaS Operator frontend to bring MaaS into the users' pockets. • The ENABLE project audit found that its MaaS platform is simple and easy to use and useful to maximise the awareness and ease of existing transport services, allowing users to plan, book & pay for journeys. Improvements were identified and the potential for learning/transfer was acknowledged. In addition, the inclusive co-design process ensured that ENABLE has a positive impact on those who currently have difficulty accessing key services, including users with mobility difficulties and other impairments that may influence travel behaviour. Collaboration with service organisations helped to ensure that the needs of diverse user groups were considered.

Obstacles or failures

Several obstacles or failures have been encountered through the implementation of the four projects. This list relies on common lacks and needs, not addressing any specific pilot:

- Lack of financial support.
- Issues to coordinate different stakeholders.
- Lack of product-market fit.
- Interoperability and compatibility.
- Unaddressed security and data management.
- Need for a mechanism for open location data.
- Lack of alignment between business and societal goals.
- Unexpected changes in legal environment.
- Lack of acceptance or understanding by certain groups of users.

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APPENDIX Y: MAAS 8

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

ITAINNOVA

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS)
Brief Description of the BM
Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) Platforms: MaaS platforms integrate multiple modes of transportation, such as public transit, ride-hailing, bike-sharing, and more, into a single app. Users can plan, book, and pay for their journeys using a combination of different transportation options.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>One of the most well-known ride-hailing services is Uber. Its success depends on its capacity to offer users convenient and reasonably priced transportation. To offer on-demand trips, Uber's business model uses cutting-edge technology and a huge network of drivers. However, Uber has encountered several difficulties, including legal obstacles, regulatory barriers, and worries about drivers' wages and labour rights.</p> <p>Users can rent cars from Zipcar, a well-known car-sharing business, for brief periods. The simple booking process, flexible rental options, and reserved parking spaces are the foundation of Zipcar's popularity. Urban areas and college campuses have seen tremendous expansion for the organisation. Maintaining fleet availability, controlling parking logistics, and competing with alternate transit choices have all been difficulties.</p> <p>Citi Bike is a scheme for sharing bicycles in New York City. It has successfully removed traffic, reduced congestion, and promoted active lifestyles. The large station network, user-friendly software, and collaborations with local authorities and advertisers are all key factors in Citi Bike's success. The availability of bikes at different stations needed to be balanced, as did maintenance and repair concerns and guaranteeing fair access in underserved areas.</p> <p>Lime is a business that rents out dockless electric scooters. Lime is successful because it takes advantage of the rising need for convenient last-mile mobility. Users can search for and hire scooters using its app-based platform. Despite its global expansion, Lime has needed help with scooter maintenance, parking regulations, and safety issues.</p> <p>Whim is a MaaS platform that unifies a variety of transportation choices into a single app, including ride-hailing, bike-sharing, and automobile rentals. Whim has established a solid reputation for offering a streamlined user experience and the ability to plan, reserve, and pay for multimodal excursions. Negotiating relationships with numerous transportation companies, assuring accurate and current information, and reaching profitability were difficulties, nevertheless.</p>
Successes
<p>Scalability: Numerous effective new and shared mobility models have demonstrated scalability by growing their business in numerous cities and nations. For instance, businesses like Uber and Lyft have established sizable networks of passengers and drivers that enable them to offer on-demand transportation services in a variety of locations all over the world. They have been able to attain a sizable user base and make a sizable amount of money because of their scalability.</p> <p>Network effects: As more users and providers join the network, the value of the service rises. This is particularly beneficial for new and shared mobility platforms. The availability of rides or automobiles increases as the user base expands, decreasing wait times and enhancing convenience. The network effect can be amplified, and the overall experience for all participants can be improved by this beneficial feedback loop, which can also draw in new users and providers.</p> <p>Gains in efficiency: Shared mobility models can boost efficiency by maximising vehicle use and lowering the need to own a car. Users can access automobiles as needed through peer-to-peer platforms like Turo and car-sharing services like Zipcar, which helps to decrease the number of vehicles on the road.</p>

This may result in improved traffic flow, reduced congestion, and reduced emissions. Studies have demonstrated that car-sharing schemes can reduce the demand for parking and the number of kilometres driven by vehicles.

Environmental benefits: By lowering the number of cars on the road and promoting the use of more environmentally friendly transportation methods, car-sharing models have the potential to support environmental sustainability. Promoting greener and more active transportation options, including biking, walking, public transportation, bike-sharing, and MaaS platforms like Whim, can help cut carbon emissions.

Governmental acceptance and support: Successful new and shared mobility models have attracted governmental approval and support in many cities and regions. Governments know the potential advantages of shared mobility in meeting transportation objectives like lowering traffic, enhancing air quality, and expanding mobility options for underserved areas. Regulations, alliances, and financing opportunities for these services may result from this assistance.

Integration with other modes: New and shared mobility services have effectively integrated with other modes to offer smooth multimodal travel options. Users can plan and pay for trips incorporating several modes, such as bus, rail, ride-hailing, and bike-sharing, using MaaS platforms like Whim. This integration streamlines the user experience, promotes mode switching, and fosters more environmentally friendly modes of transportation.

The KPIs may include statistics on users, journeys, vehicle miles travelled, decreases in private vehicle ownership, increases in trips made by public transportation, decreases in emissions, and changes in travel habits.

Obstacles or failures

Goal misalignment between business and social objectives: One of the largest obstacles is the need to match the objectives of mobility service providers more effectively with overarching social objectives. For instance, the company strategy may have a negative effect on the environment and underserved areas if it puts profit before sustainability or ignores social fairness. Long-term success depends on balancing corporate objectives and social and environmental concerns.

Confined space in cities: Urban areas frequently need more room, which makes it challenging for innovative and shared mobility services to function efficiently. Significant obstacles can arise when it comes to accommodating bike-share stations, finding parking for shared vehicles, or removing scooter debris. In densely crowded cities, a lack of space might restrict scalability and prevent service expansion.

Issues to coordinate different stakeholders: Implementing and running new and shared mobility services sometimes calls for collaboration among numerous parties, including governmental organisations, transit authorities, commercial businesses, and community organisations. These groups' inability to coordinate and work together can result in regulatory issues, disagreements over infrastructure, and problems building an efficient transportation system.

Lack of communication between government organisations and providers of mobility services: Implementation success depends on effective communication and cooperation between government organisations and mobility service providers. When there are no specific rules, regulations, or ongoing communication between the two parties, problems develop. This can result from uncertainty, regulatory challenges, and trouble obtaining the required permits or licenses.

Lack of acceptance or comprehension among some user groups: Some users may be unwilling to use new or shared mobility services. While some people may be hesitant to adopt new technology, others may have mobility needs that the currently offered services must appropriately meet. Addressing these issues through user education, specialised services, and user feedback methods is crucial to removing these obstacles.

Lack of product-market fit: Shared and new mobility services must provide solutions that address the demands and preferences of their target demographics. Low adoption rates and low user involvement might result from failing to adapt the product to the market, for instance, because the services provided are too expensive, not convenient enough, or do not solve difficulties.

Low user affordability: In low-income areas, affordability is a significant hurdle for many. Shared mobility services' accessibility and inclusiveness may be constrained if their price is high compared to other forms of transportation. Long-term success depends on striking a balance between affordability and viable business concepts.

Technology Obstacles: Technology infrastructure, such as mobile apps, payment systems, and fleet management platforms, is crucial for new and shared mobility services. The user experience can be negatively impacted by technological issues like system failures, app bugs, or cybersecurity concerns, which can erode customer confidence in the business.

High level of competition: Many firms are seeking market share in the New and Shared Mobility sector, which is very competitive. Intense competition may result in challenges with brand loyalty, reduced profit margins, and pricing pressure. Differentiation through special offerings, high-quality service, and a positive user experience is crucial to stand out in a crowded market.

Unexpected legal environment changes: The legal and regulatory framework for innovative and shared mobility services is subject to unpredictable changes. Changes in license requirements, insurance specifications, data protection laws, or labour laws can provide substantial difficulties for service providers and necessitate flexibility and adherence to the changing legal landscape.

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APPENDIX Z: MICROMOBILITY 1

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Forum Virium Helsinki
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
B2C shared cargo bikes for shopping
Brief Description of the BM
Free-floating shared cargo bikes in a residential area (and shopping centre) as an addition to the existing city bike system.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
Nezeco / Colossus Finland (Jätkäsaari Cargo Bikes)
Successes
Got subsequent pilots (with two different innovation competitions and minor funding) with tens of users
Obstacles or failures
Did not make it to continuous operation after pilots.
References
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APPENDIX AA: MICROMOBILITY 2

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	European Passengers' Federation
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Business-to-consumer (B2C) shared micromobility
Brief Description of the BM
A business owns a fleet of micromobility vehicles, such as bikes or scooters, that can be rented out to its members, either by the minute, hour, or day.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>Dott: operates more than 50,000 shared e-scooters and e-bikes in more than 35 cities in Europe and Israel.</p> <p>Blue-bike: has more than 2,500 shared bikes in 110 locations in Belgian transport hubs. OV-fiets, similarly to Blue-bike, is available at more than 300 locations in the Netherlands, allowing train users to hire a bike for the last mile of their journey. Call a Bike is Deutsche Bahn's nationwide bike-sharing service – and one of the largest and most successful in Germany with more than 13,000 rental bikes in 80 cities and municipalities throughout Germany.</p> <p>Lime: is the world's largest shared electric vehicle company. They are on a mission to build a future where transportation is shared, affordable, and carbon-free. They provide convenient and reliable short-term rentals of electric bikes and scooters at an affordable price in more than 200 cities in nearly 30 countries on five continents including Europe.</p> <p>Voi Technology: is a micro-mobility startup that provides electric scooters for last-mile transportation. They create a system of electrically powered scooters around urban centres to provide a way to commute while helping people reduce their carbon footprint and cities to have a more sustainable transportation network.</p>
Successes
<p>Integration with other transport modes: shared micromobility, such as scooters and bikes, offers door-to-door mobility options for short trips. Some providers, like Blue-bike or OV-fiets, are located in mobility hubs, thus offering an integrated solution for the first and last mile of a journey.</p> <p>Convenience: shared micromobility solutions can be rented 24/7. Some micromobility providers are free-floating, meaning that they keep their vehicles in many locations throughout a city, thus making them easily accessible.</p> <p>Diverse payment plans: many companies offer the possibility to pay per ride or get a pass/subscription. The price may also be cheaper and more convenient than that of public transport or car use.</p> <p>Less maintenance and costs: management and maintenance of the vehicles are done by the service provider. Dott, for example, also offers complementary insurance to its riders in some countries.</p> <p>Scalability: according to EIT Urban Mobility, free-floating shared micromobility schemes have expanded to more than 50% of European cities in 5 years.</p> <p>Positive impact on CO₂ emissions: CO₂ emissions from shared micromobility are lower than private car trips or ride-hailing services.</p> <p>Reduction of congestion: because shared micromobility can be a potential substitution for car trips, it can help reduce congestion.</p> <p>User-friendly apps: for instance, Lime's success lies in its user-friendly mobile app, making it easier for users to access their services.</p>
Obstacles or failures

Difficult rental and membership terms: some terms may be unclear to users, and quite often, a membership is needed before a person can rent a bike or a scooter. Some rental terms may also be complicated for potential users to understand. As an example, the Blue-bike process for unlocking a bike varies depending on the location. For example, at rental points with a key dispenser, the user needs a membership card to unlock the bike, while at other rental points where the bikes have digital locks, the user needs an app.

Limited availability: in some hubs or stations, the vehicles may be fully rented out. For some rentals, like Blue-bikes, there is also a maximum amount of time that a bike can be rented.

Accessibility barriers: the majority of shared micromobility users are young, able-bodied, and tech-savvy. A number of individuals, such as the elderly, and people with physical disabilities are not often considered in the design of these micromobility systems and do not get the chance to benefit from them. Additionally, to access a shared micromobility service, a user generally needs to download and use an app on his/her mobile phone. This can be difficult for people who are not technologically savvy or for people who do not even own a smartphone. Lastly, many shared micromobility solutions include payment by bank card, which may be a barrier for some people.

Limitations with fixed stations: some micromobility providers may only have one location in a city. Blue-bikes, for example, are generally located at mobility hubs or train stations, with only one location in a city. This may be more convenient for people commuting for the day (e.g., to and from work) but is not convenient for other people who would like to travel to another area of the city and stay there. Blue-bike also adds a surcharge if a bike is returned to a different hub than where it was picked up.

Spatial limitations: some cities offer dedicated parking spots for bikes and scooters alike, however, others do not offer scooter parking. There is a need for better cooperation between rental companies and municipal authorities to manage sidewalk and curb areas. Furthermore, companies like Dott provide guidelines on where and how to properly park their scooters, however, not all users abide by these guidelines. This often leads to users parking scooters on the sidewalk, which causes obstructions that are inconvenient and dangerous for pedestrians.

Additional challenges: scooter maintenance, user safety concerns (a lot of people are involved in accidents), and regulatory compliance in various cities.

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APPENDIX BB: MICROMOBILITY 3

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Capital Region of Denmark
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
B2C bike-sharing system
Brief Description of the BM
<p>Bycyklen. Bike Share system in Copenhagen and Frederiksberg</p> <p>The shared e-bikes scheme was implemented in 2014. Docking-based system located mainly by metro and train stations. 132 city bike stations in 17 different cities and neighbourhoods in and around Copenhagen. A total of 1,400 city bikes were part of the network that could be rented by the minute with an app.</p> <p>The organisation behind Bycyklen consisted of: Bikeshare Danmark A/S (the operating company that owns all hardware and is responsible for operation and customer service), Bycyklen IT (a subsidiary of Bikeshare, which is responsible for maintenance and development of the fleet management system behind the Bycykelsysteme) and The Commuter Bicycle Foundation (a private, commercial foundation founded by the contributors DSB, the Municipality of Copenhagen and the Municipality of Frederiksberg)</p> <p>Together with buses, trains, and metro, it was the goal that the city bikes should be the fourth leg of public transport. But the city bikes were a resounding failure. Despite large subsidies of a total of DKK 96 million, both the fund and the operating company have suffered losses and negative equity.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>In 2022, the company was declared bankrupt, and the bikes and stations were left untouched in the urban space. The city bike has never been the success it was expected to be and in recent years has been overtaken by a number of private bicycle and scooter operators offering more modern transport options. As a result, the white bikes and the 'clunky' racks/docking stations they sit in are seen by many as useless in the cityscape.</p>
Successes
<p>Perhaps the biggest success of the city bikes was the ability to place permanent stations in strategic good locations for first and last-mile transport to and from public transport. It was also one of the first schemes in the world with e-bikes. It had good integration with public transport hubs and the whole idea of a shared bicycle system was tested on a large scale and paved the road for new private providers such as BOLT, Donkey Republic, Lime, and TIER who have pushed city bikes in Copenhagen and other cities even further.</p>
Obstacles or failures
<p>A system that was limited in its reach. Not all municipalities in the Region were a part of the city bike system, which in practice meant that there were gaps and inconsistencies in terms of accessibility of the system across municipalities.</p> <p>The system went bankrupt due to a lack of user revenue. The system was never at any point very popular among the citizens.</p> <p>Lack of flexibility of stationary docking stations.</p> <p>The city bike has never been the success it was expected to be and in recent years has been overtaken by a number of private bicycle and scooter operators offering more modern and flexible transport options. As a result, the white bikes and the 'clunky' racks/docking stations they sit in are seen by many as useless in the cityscape.</p>
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APPENDIX CC: MOBILITY HUB

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING

Porto Digital

New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
<p><i>One example is the pilot mobility station in Munich. This mobility station, introduced in November 2014, is a hub with a public transport station, as well as parking places reserved for car-sharing vehicles and a bike-sharing station (Pfertner et al., 2017).</i></p> <p>The article discusses the impact of car sharing in Munich, Germany, based on a survey among its users. Key findings revealed that car sharing led to a reduction in car ownership and vehicle kilometres travelled, with users appreciating the service due to cost savings, flexibility, and its environmentally friendly aspect. The demographic profile of the respondents is also highlighted in the article. MVG Rad bikes, another mode of shared transportation, are briefly mentioned too. However, the text provided does not provide details about the "Mobility Station."</p> <p>The text discusses the use of a Mobility Station that integrates multiple mobility services, including public transportation (PT) and free-floating car sharing (FFCS), as well as a smartphone application (MVG More) that provides location and availability information about the services. It also discusses the potential for further tariff integration and the creation of mobility packages to promote multimodality, suggesting business models related to intermodal transportation, shared mobility, and integrated mobility service platforms.</p>
Brief Description of the BM
<p>The business model implemented in this context is the integration of various mobility services, such as public transportation and free-floating car sharing, within the concept of a Mobility Station. Information about the location and availability of these services is provided via a smartphone application, called MVG More. The model aims at promoting multimodal transportation, providing users with more flexible, efficient, and convenient mobility options. Part of this business model also includes the potential for tariff integration and the creation of mobility packages to further promote multimodal transportation solutions.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented and successes and failures that have been reported
<p>The text does not specify any case studies or reports on successes and failures where the business model of the Mobility Station has been implemented. The excerpt focuses more on the general development and evaluation of the "Mobility Station" project in the City of Munich and its effects on multimodal mobility, user acceptance, and behaviours.</p>
Successes
<p>Potential benefits inherent to such a business model that integrates various mobility services might include:</p> <p>Scalability: The model could potentially be replicated in other urban areas, accommodating the specific transportation demands of those locations.</p> <p>Network Effects: As more users adopt these integrated services, their value and utility for users will increase.</p> <p>Efficiency Gains: An integrated service could offer improved logistical efficiency, enabling smoother transitions between different types of transport.</p> <p>Environmental Advantages: By promoting the use of public transport and shared mobility options, this model could contribute to the reduction of individual car usage and thus decrease emissions.</p>

Political Acceptance and Support: These projects often align with wider urban sustainability and smart city goals, possibly gaining support from local government.

Integration with Other Transport Modes: The very objective of the model is to seamlessly combine multiple transportation options, providing diverse and flexible mobility choices for users.

Obstacles or failures

Potential challenges to this type of business model might include:

Misalignment of Business and Societal Goals: Profit-oriented mobility service providers might face conflicts with societal goals like access for all users or reduction in carbon emissions.

Limited Urban Space: In crowded city centres, it might be hard to find sufficient space to install comprehensive Mobility Stations.

Coordination Difficulties: Coordinating multiple stakeholders, each with their own interests and constraints, is a complex task that may cause conflict or slow progress.

Communication Issues: Lack of effective communication between public authorities and mobility service providers could result in misaligned expectations or unmet goals.

User Acceptance/Understanding: Users might resist adopting new habits or may not understand the benefits of the new service, leading to lower-than-expected uptake.

Lack of Product-Market Fit: The product or service might not meet the actual needs of the passenger, leading to low adoption rates.

Technological Challenges: The integration of various mobility services might encounter technical issues.

Unforeseen Legal Changes: Changes in the legal environment could affect operations or the viability of the project.

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APPENDIX DD: OTHER 1

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Forum Virium Helsinki
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
B2C leisure boat sharing
Brief Description of the BM
Fleet of motor boats (petrol and electric) to use in several locations with a monthly subscription model
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
Skipperi / City Boat
Successes
Fast growth and happy customers thanks to a good concept and superb service design. Leisure boats are ideal for sharing as they are expensive but not for everyday use – and are located in boat harbours anyway. Big investment by Yamaha Motor Europe and thanks to that has expanded from Finland to Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Canada, and New Zealand.
Obstacles or failures
Surprisingly minor problems only. Ideal for day-time short boat journeys several times during the summer – not for longer overnight journeys or only some one or two times a year. Also, peer-to-peer sharing at Skipperi for those kinds of purposes.
References
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APPENDIX EE: OTHER 2

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Forum Virium Helsinki
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
B2C on-demand electric boat with a half-fixed route
Brief Description of the BM
Electric boat to several nearby island destinations – procured by the city plus a reasonably priced ticket for passengers.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
Callboats
Successes
Met the demand for electric boat connection from the City of Helsinki participatory budgeting and the city's maritime strategy. Got 6,000 paying customers/passengers already in its first pilot in the year 2020 and then a more established position to serve several islands in the Helsinki archipelago. Initial international sales. Got funding and is working towards developing autonomous driving of the boats.
Obstacles or failures
Boat models for now have been 6-12 passengers, which is smaller than usual water buses. May be a bit costly if not enough passengers – as boats are a bit expensive and the season is quite short in many places. Takes some pilots and negotiations to find the right routes or operating areas where it would meet the demand.
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APPENDIX FF: RIDESHARING 1

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Forum Virium Helsinki
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Sports club ride to training
Brief Description of the BM
Kids' ride straight from school to hobbies – getting cheaper shifts at sports halls thanks to earlier starting times
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
PPJ Pelikyty
Successes
Ingenious basic idea as it gains economic benefits from cheaper times at sports halls – and that money can be used for transportation that frees up times for parents.
Obstacles or failures
Did not get any operator to continue the service for the sports club. Was not coordinated by professionals who would have time to develop the service further. Was not very interesting from the minibus company either – as afternoons are their rush hour and enough customers anyway.
References
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APPENDIX GG: RIDESHARING 2

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	European Passengers' Federation
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Peer-to-Peer (P2P) ridesharing
Brief Description of the BM
Peer-to-Peer ridesharing is a transportation model where users offer or seek rides in personal vehicles, often facilitated through online platforms or mobile applications. This business model enables drivers with available seats in their cars to offer rides to passengers heading in the same direction, typically for a fee that helps cover expenses (e.g., gas). Passengers can find rides based on their destination and schedule, often at lower costs than with traditional public transport options.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>BlaBlaCar: remains one of the world's largest long-distance ridesharing platforms that connects cities and regions. It connects drivers with free seats in their vehicles with passengers. Due to its success, BlaBlaCar extended its service offer with bus rides via BlaBlaBus (Ouibus).</p> <p>Mpact (Taxistop): works on a more efficient and accessible mobility system based on the principle 'do more with less'. They work towards more energy efficiency, inclusion, social cohesion, and less traffic jams, emissions, costs, etc. They develop and launch their own services. A few examples are Carpool, MobiCalendar, and Mobitwin (see also below). They ensure that their mobility services are connected with other modes of transport – e.g., public transport – and with each other.</p> <p>Mobitwin: is a Belgian volunteer-based service that connects people with reduced mobility to voluntary drivers in an effort to help avoid social isolation. Mobitwin is often organised at the local level by either a municipality or a public social welfare center. Currently, there are 275 "Mobitwin Desks", which are spread across the Belgian regions of Flanders, Wallonia, and Brussels.</p> <p>Uber: is an American transportation conglomerate that mainly provides ridesharing services where individuals can hail a vehicle using the Uber app on their smartphones. Uber operates in about 10,000 cities across the world.</p> <p>Other ridesharing apps include Lyft (US and Canada), Freenow (Europe), Bolt (Europe, Asia, and Latin America), and Cabify (Spain and Latin America).</p>
Successes
<p>Environmental benefits: by filling empty seats in vehicles, P2P ridesharing can reduce the overall number of vehicles on the road, leading to potential environmental benefits through reduced congestion and emissions.</p> <p>Cost savings: P2P ridesharing often offers more affordable transportation options compared to traditional public transport, making it more appealing to cost-conscious users.</p> <p>Community building: ride-sharing platforms often foster a sense of community by connecting individuals who share common destinations. This creates social interactions and reduces the sense of isolation during travelling.</p> <p>Diverse offer for reserving a ride: Offering a variety of methods for reserving rides is important for the inclusion of a diverse range of users. Ridesharing services like Uber allow people to book a ride via a smartphone app, the phone, or a website.</p>
Obstacles or failures
<p>Safety & trust: both drivers and passengers may have concerns about trust and safety when using P2P ridesharing services, considering most rides are shared with strangers. However, some ridesharing services, like BlaBlaCar, offer "rating services", where members give and receive ratings from other members after travelling together. Uber offers a similar rating system between drivers and passengers. Such functions can help improve feelings of trust.</p>

Regulatory challenges: the regulatory environment for P2P ridesharing can vary widely by location. Some regions may have stricter regulations that make it difficult for ridesharing platforms to operate.

Driver & vehicle quality: quality and maintenance standards of vehicles can vary among P2P ridesharing providers and individual drivers, which might affect the experience of using these services.

Insurance issues: challenges of understanding insurance coverage and liability in case of accidents or incidents can be complex.

Availability: the availability of rides can vary depending on time and location, which might not be as reliable as traditional taxi services, especially in remote areas.

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APPENDIX HH: RIDESHARING 3

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Via Verde
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Carpooling platform-based business models
Brief Description of the BM
<p>Via Verde Boleias, a carpooling system deployed in Portugal.</p> <p>"Via Verde Boleias" was a Portuguese carpooling service that aimed to connect drivers and passengers for shared rides. It was launched as an initiative to reduce traffic congestion, promote carpooling, and contribute to environmental sustainability.</p> <p>Via Verde Boleias operated as a web-based platform and a mobile app, enabling users to register as either drivers or passengers. Drivers would offer available seats in their vehicles for passengers heading in the same direction. Passengers could then browse available rides, select the most suitable option, and book a seat for a shared journey.</p> <p>Users would gain access to Via Verde Boleias through the app or online. Users would register and fill out some information to identify themselves as a driver and/or passenger. Like other transit apps, this service allowed users to rate drivers and passengers.</p> <p>People could form themselves into public or private groups during these exchanges. Public groups were formed primarily for special events such as festivals, concerts, or popular weekend destinations. Private groups, perfect for commuting, were intended for those who work for the same company or university.</p> <p>When drivers posted the trip they would like to share, they established a price. The fee was the same for all passengers, regardless of quantity, and Via Verde Boleias recommended it to ensure that expenses were evenly distributed.</p> <p>Drivers should promote journeys as if they were advertisements, describing the number of seats available, the dates and points of departure and arrival. Reservations were required for passengers.</p> <p>Any driver could sign up for this service, regardless of whether they were a Via Verde customer or had the OBU installed in their vehicle. Everyone could use the platform for free.</p> <p>In terms of benefits and compensations, the driver received €5 in fuel on the first ride and up to €3 on subsequent journeys; the passenger received €5 to spend at a well-known supermarket chain (Pingo Doce).</p> <p>In 2019 an important campaign for the NOVA 'FCT' University students and employees was launched. Through this campaign, Via Verde intended to offer drivers 50 Fnac (tech products) online vouchers worth €30 each, and passengers 100 Fnac online vouchers worth €10 each.</p> <p>This campaign was valid for the first users of the NOVA FCT closed group who, as drivers, would take 5 (five) rides with 1 (one) or more passengers, in addition to the driver, via the "Via Verde Boleias" app or website. This campaign was valid for the first users of the group.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
Portugal
Successes
Via Verde Boleias achieved notable successes, particularly within the community of NOVA FCT University in Almada. The platform facilitated the creation of active carpooling groups within the university and other communities. Users found the application to be efficient and convenient, contributing to an increase in shared rides.

One significant achievement was the positive impact on the environment. According to calculations by Via Verde Boleias, each shared trip resulted in a 75% reduction in CO₂ emissions, reflecting the service's contribution to environmental sustainability.

Additionally, Via Verde Boleias served as a valuable database for the Via Verde Vantagens program, enhancing the overall benefits for Via Verde customers.

Obstacles or failures

Despite its successes, Via Verde Boleias faced challenges in achieving a balanced supply and demand. While there were many willing drivers, the platform struggled to attract a sufficient number of passengers, leading to an imbalance in the user base.

One of the obstacles was the target audience for communication. The primary focus was on Via Verde's existing customers, who typically owned their vehicles. These customers were less inclined to use carpooling services, as they already had personal vehicles. This challenge limited the expansion of the user base beyond the Via Verde customer segment.

Over time, as communities and universities developed their carpooling routines and arrangements, the platform became less relevant to their needs, as they relied on established carpooling networks.

In summary, Via Verde Boleias succeeded in fostering carpooling within specific communities and reducing CO₂ emissions. However, it encountered difficulties in achieving a balanced user base and attracting customers beyond the Via Verde customer segment, ultimately leading to the discontinuation of the service.

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APPENDIX II: RIDESHARING 4

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	Via Verde
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
Car sharing platform-based business models
Brief Description of the BM
<p>DriveNow, a car-sharing solution deployed in Lisbon in 2017.</p> <p>DriveNow powered by Via Verde, a collaboration between the BMW Group and Sixt SE, launched its car-sharing service in Lisbon in June 2017.</p> <p>This venture was made possible through a partnership with Brisa, a leading mobility infrastructure provider, while Brisa – under its subsidiary Via Verde – was operating on a franchise basis. DriveNow aimed to address Lisbon's traffic congestion and emissions challenges by introducing a fleet of 211 vehicles, featuring BMW and MINI models. These vehicles covered a substantial initial service area of 48 square kilometres, spanning the city from East to West and North to South.</p> <p>One key aspect of DriveNow was its commitment to providing premium vehicles at affordable prices – 29 cents per minute. It enabled users to access these vehicles with ease, fostering the idea of shared mobility in Lisbon.</p>
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
Lisbon
Successes
<p>DriveNow experienced notable successes during its presence in Lisbon.</p> <p>The launch received considerable national attention, and it gained the enthusiastic support of the Lisbon Municipal Council. The city was particularly engaged in promoting shared mobility solutions due to the Web Summit's influence, resulting in the creation of additional car-sharing spaces to accommodate the service. Lisbon aimed to set an example for last-mile transportation solutions.</p> <p>Before the official launch, DriveNow had already attracted over 7,000 registrations in Lisbon, indicating a high level of initial interest in the service. Furthermore, DriveNow allowed users to access a comprehensive car-sharing experience, including fuel, insurance, and parking, all via a user-friendly mobile app.</p>
Obstacles or failures
<p>Despite its successes, DriveNow faced several challenges during its operation in Lisbon. Initially, the car-sharing market in Lisbon had limited competition, with only a few players such as CityDrive. While Emov (PSA Group) later entered the market, offering smaller cars, DriveNow faced unexpected competition from ShareToGo (Mercedes) which posed additional challenges.</p> <p>Moreover, the car-sharing market in Lisbon had unique dynamics. There were approximately 3,000 taxis and nearly 2,000 Uber vehicles, while DriveNow launched with 200 cars. This limited fleet size meant that DriveNow couldn't fully meet the city's demand for car-sharing services.</p> <p>Another significant challenge was the rapid growth of ride-hailing companies like Uber and Bolt, which provided cost-effective and convenient rides in Lisbon. This shift in consumer behaviour and preferences impacted the demand for car-sharing.</p> <p>Lastly, the logistical complexities of fleet distribution, including car maintenance and cleaning, presented operational challenges.</p> <p>Ultimately, DriveNow merged with ShareNow (formerly car2go) as part of an industry consolidation, which marked the conclusion of its operations in Lisbon.</p>
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APPENDIX JJ: SAAS

GEMINI PARTNER REPORTING	ATOM mobility
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New and Shared mobility Business model (BM)
<p>ATOM Mobility - Software as a service (SaaS), B2B works on the following products -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle sharing software • Ride-hail software • Digital rental software
Brief Description of the BM
<p>Core products: vehicle sharing software, digital rental software, ride-hailing software.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle sharing software – suited for any type of sharing: scooters, bikes, mopeds, motorcycles, vans, cars, and others. • Ride hail - all the technology needed to launch your own ride-hailing or taxi business. Cars, vans, trucks, rickshaws, boats and more. • Rental - cars, e-cars, e-bikes. Short and long-term booking with a calendar to pick the times.
Case studies where the BM has been implemented
<p>One of ATOM's key accounts is Qick, which is using a vehicle-sharing platform. They launched operations back in 2019 and currently operating in more than 15 cities in Sweden.</p> <p><u>Success:</u> In a shared mobility world, they are quite a big company, with thousands of vehicles in 15+ cities at this moment. Its success mainly depends on locations as well as a strong local presence (being a Swedish company, operating in Sweden, vs international players like Lime, Voi, Bolt, etc).</p> <p><u>Failures:</u> Qick have added a new city of Operations where they have operated for a couple of months. Due to bad user behaviour, there were a lot of bad parking cases. As a result, there were fines from the city. Smart parking analysis integration was not available at that time and Qick had to stop the operations in this city.</p>
Successes
<p>The main successes from ATOM operators -</p> <p>Scalability: The biggest moped-sharing provider in Latvia plans to expand its operations to other Baltic countries (Lithuania and Estonia). In addition, it plans to expand to other countries all around the Baltic Sea.</p> <p>Environmental advantages: scooter-sharing provider in Ukraine that is located in the city of Kyiv. They want the capital of Ukraine to become a greener city. Kyiv government has benefitted a lot from ATOM operators' insights into their city and also how people are using the micromobility. The company's mission is to expand the fleet and add other vehicle types like mopeds, bikes, and electric cars.</p>
Obstacles or failures
<p>Lack of user acceptance: for another operator of ours, customers were not used to vehicle-sharing service, merchant was the first provider in the country in Latin America. As a result, merchant encountered problems with operations due to local customers not being very accustomed to the service. Sales targets were not being met and a lot of investment has gone into the business without projected turnover being reached.</p> <p>High competition: Two vehicle-sharing providers in Romania and Ukraine were faced with competition problems in their countries. Two sharing providers had business failures due to competition, when a large, well-known vehicle-sharing provider entered the market, their sales dropped dramatically. In addition, for the cities, it is not a good thing either, because the competition will drive prices down, and small operators might need to stop their operations. As a result, the city will be left with one big operator who is not following the rules or needs as they are in a monopoly. So, it would be recommended for the city to have tenders that give a fair chance to all sized companies.</p>

Lack of understanding by certain groups of users: Moped-sharing businesses in Latvia faced issues with vandalism. People's attitude is the biggest challenge for them. There are several broken mechanical components, and smashed screens and since these details must be constantly ordered, it creates huge costs. Many people do not value the work of others.

Technological challenges: many ATOM operators have tried to build their own software without previous experience or used a lesser quality software provider, for example in India. For the solution to get widely adapted by populations and be able to comply with the local rules and regulations, the software capabilities are one of the main keys to success.

At some point, their team decided to change the software provided and chose ATOM. Now with a new app, they are getting a significant number of new users as the registration is a lot faster.

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APPENDIX KK: SURVEY

